

It's Like We Forgot Who We Are.

Lawyers in The Know. Lawyers among Fog. Lawyers with Passion and Courage. Not Caretakers.¹

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Abstract

We're here to remind us who we are. Today one of the few subjects on which we all seem to agree is the need for justice and peace. But why our agreement for justice and peace leads to war and injustice? Maybe, our agreement is only seeming. Now we ask ourselves: maybe that war that we are experiencing now is because we have not listened to, we have not tasted, isn't it? We refer to quantum physics to answer the question. The quantum physics has been arrived by thinking and experimenting to revolutionizing knowledges, which determine our world, also if only few have understood these theories in their real sense. We follow the question, whether and how far a consciousness trained by quantum physics can reach more directly to the understanding of questions of life and peaceful questions than a thinking, which is obliged to classical legal education. It deals especially with fundamental existential questions: the theme of personal responsibility, the value of the individual existence, the evaluation of the personal I-you relation. The connections of natural sciences and peace, ecology, and sociological change have always driven us. How can we speech about that, which science cannot comprehend? What means self, identity, responsibility, peace for the lawyer and the quantum physicist? We offer you an exciting meeting.

Keywords: peace, justice, liberty, state, church, war, crisis, listen to, taste, perception, comprehension, knowing, aion, kairos, kronos, Russophobia, creative justice, judicial discretion, QFT, biocentrism, nothingness, emptiness

"It's like we forgot who we are.
Explorers. Pioneers.
Not caretakers"³

- the movie Interstellar.

"Hopelessness is the enemy of justice"
- Bryan Stevenson⁴

#DedicatedtoEqualJusticeInitiative

Introduction. Carlo Rovelli, Luciano Canfora, Alessandro Orsini ... and other philosophers and historians disagree with Europe's position on the war in Ukraine.⁵

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² <https://www.ponticelloapartments.com/?lang=en>

³ <https://www.slelaworld.com/olga-nickole-kuyan>

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G0Wltu5hfPU>

⁴ Bryan Stevenson (1959) is an American lawyer, social justice activist, founder/executive director of the Equal Justice Initiative, and a law professor at New York University School of Law. Based in Montgomery, Alabama, he has challenged bias against the poor and minorities in the criminal justice system, especially children. He has helped achieve United States Supreme Court decisions that prohibit sentencing children under 18 to death or to life imprisonment without parole. He has assisted in cases that have saved dozens of prisoners from the death penalty, advocated for the poor, and developed community-based reform litigation aimed at improving the administration of criminal justice.

⁵ <https://pledgetimes.com/ukrainian-war-camphor-co-theorists-of-neither-nor-among-the-5s-skeptical-about-mariupol/>

Today one of the few subjects on which we all seem to agree is the need for justice and peace. But why our agreement for justice and peace leads to war and injustice? Maybe, our agreement is only seeming. Now we ask ourselves: maybe the war that we are experiencing now is because we have not listened to, we have not tasted, isn't it? Devoting this paper to the Whole, to the Consciousness, we start from Ranjan Gogoi, Justice for the judge (2021) that has generated a lot of heat and controversy among lawyers/judges. Today we need to overcome the war, the crisis consciousnessly. We consider consciousness a quantum field, starting from F. Faggin who contemplates particles not as objects, but as "states of fields".

Findings and recommendations about how we can minimise war's, crisis's impact on Peace and Justice facing challenge. But let's unpack the notion of justice in the context of current war events.

Reinhold Niebuhr⁶ said that "Love is the motive, but justice is the instrument."⁷ We say: Love is the motive, but peace is the the instrument.

Anti-Russian hatred has risen significantly in Europe in recent months. In recent years anti-Muslim hatred has risen significantly in Europe.

Our Initiative protects people from the war and injustice as well as supports lawyers committed to such things.

The Human Rights and Access to Justice Program⁸ protects individuals from discrimination, violence, injustice, and corruption, as well as supports international human rights bodies committed to such protection.

Russophobia spreads following the Russia-Ukraine War.⁹ Far-right extremism and xenophobia have fueled Islamophobia in Western countries, where terrorist attacks by Daesh and al-Qaida as well as a migrant crisis are used as excuses to legitimize those views. To combat a rising tide of Islamophobia in France, the Government organized 18 Islamic Art Exhibitions Nationwide.¹⁰ To combat a rising tide of Russophobia in Europe, we support Veryovka Ukrainian National Honoured Academic Folk Choir¹¹ and Helikon Opera.¹²

When we say that we advocate peace and justice, we don't specify what we have in mind. This is especially so today, when so many advocate peace and justice — often with great passion, but with no definition. All peace and justice is inherently social. Can someone on a desert island be either peaceful or just or unjust?

We're here today to remind us who we are. We must overcome the war, the crisis consciousnessly.

6 Karl Paul Reinhold Niebuhr[a] (1892–1971) was an American Reformed theologian, ethicist, commentator on politics and public affairs, and professor at Union Theological Seminary for more than 30 years. Niebuhr was one of America's leading public intellectuals for several decades of the 20th century and received the Presidential Medal of Freedom in 1964. A public theologian, he wrote and spoke frequently about the intersection of religion, politics, and public policy, with his most influential books including *Moral Man and Immoral Society* and *The Nature and Destiny of Man*. The latter is ranked number 18 of the top 100 non-fiction books of the twentieth century by Modern Library. Andrew Bacevich labelled Niebuhr's book *The Irony of American History* "the most important book ever written on U.S. foreign policy." The historian Arthur Schlesinger Jr. described Niebuhr as "the most influential American theologian of the 20th century" and *Time* posthumously called Niebuhr "the greatest Protestant theologian in America since Jonathan Edwards."

7 <https://www.azquotes.com/quote/913696#:~:text=Reinhold%20Niebuhr%20quote%3A%20Love%20is,but%20justice%20is%20the%20instrument.>

8 <https://www.vancecenter.org/areas-of-practice/human-rights-and-access-to-justice/#:~:text=The%20Human%20Rights%20and%20Access,bodies%20committed%20to%20such%20protection.>

9 <https://politicstoday.org/russophobia-spreads-following-the-russia-ukraine-war/>

10 <https://www.euronews.com/culture/2021/11/18/no-single-place-or-medium-france-spotlights-islamic-art-in-bold-country-wide-exhibits>

11 <https://veryovka.com/en/#:~:text=Veryovka%20Ukrainian%20National%20Honoured%20Academic,Ukraine%20by%20their%20perfect%20art.>

12 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Helikon_Opera

Today we pay attention to Lautsi case¹³ again, because we celebrate Italy. December 2021 European Commission tried to 'cancel' Christmas, recommending to replace the greeting "Merry Christmas" with "Happy Holidays"¹⁴ and Italy was *contro* this EU recommendation, responding that this is not the way to fight discrimination,¹⁵ this is not just way. We say: '*Viva l'Italia!*' and, looking beyond, we comprehend that today we need to overcome the war, the crisis. Today, frontline reports, good and bad news about various facts with peaceful and national connotations come from Ukraine and different countries: an image of Kiev is devastated by the Russians¹⁶; despite a string of measures intended to cut numbers, more than 27,000 crossed the Channel in small boats year 2021;¹⁷ the one-year-old baby died in the woods of Polish-Belarusian borderland¹⁸; Northern Ireland footballer has nightmares over abuse, court hears¹⁹; in the English Channel disaster at least 27 refugees drowned in the waters separating France and the United Kingdom²⁰; three mosques were targeted in the latest series of Islamophobic attacks in France²¹; the eight men, now in their 40s and 50s, have made damages claims against Manchester City and say Bennell abused them²²; French President Macron has slammed UK PM Johnson over his handling of the crisis while NGOs raise alarm²³; Human rights are being attacked by the government, not fine-tuned.²⁴ John Robinson²⁵ fears that we are facing an existential attack on our democracy, the inability of the people and the courts to hold the government to account. Nick Moss²⁶ says the struggle to defend and extend our rights has to be conducted on the streets, as well as in parliament and the courts. The list is endless. Also the Church is seeking peace and justice²⁷, while sometimes not agreeing on a state acting which the state finds just. So, in Russia in the spring of 2020, one could observe

13 On March 18, 2011, the European Court of Human Rights, sitting as a Grand Chamber ("GC"), pronounced its judgment in the case of *Soile Lautsi and Others v. Italy*. (*Lautsi v. Italy*, App. No. 30814/06, 2011 Eur. Ct. H.R. (G.C.) By this final judgment, which overturned a unanimous judgment rendered on November 3, 2009, by the Second Section of the Strasbourg Court (A Section is an administrative entity, and a Chamber is a judicial formation of the Court within a given Section. The Court has five Sections in which Chambers are formed. Each Section has a President, a Vice-President, and a number of other judges), the Grand Chamber (The Grand Chamber is made up of 17 judges: the Court's President and Vice-Presidents, the Section Presidents, and the national judge, together with other judges selected by drawing of lots. The initiation of proceedings before the Grand Chamber takes two different forms: referral and relinquishment. After a Chamber judgment has been delivered, the parties may request referral of the case to the Grand Chamber and such requests are accepted on an exceptional basis. A panel of judges of the Grand Chamber decides whether or not the case should be referred to the Grand Chamber for fresh consideration. Cases are also sent to the Grand Chamber when relinquished by a Chamber, although this is also exceptional. The Chamber to which a case is assigned can relinquish it to the Grand Chamber if the case raises a serious question affecting the interpretation of the Convention or if there is a risk of inconsistency with a previous judgment of the Court. See The Court, EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS, (Aug. 4, 2012, 3:18 PM),

<http://www.echr.coe.int/ECHR/EN/Header/The+Court/The+Court/The+Grand+Chamber/>) decided, by fifteen votes to two, that the compulsory display of crucifixes in Italian State-school classrooms did not violate Article 2 of the first Protocol of the European Convention on Human Rights. (*Lautsi*, 2011 Eur. Ct. H.R. §§ 77–78)

14 <https://www.euronews.com/2021/11/30/eu-draft-pulled-after-vatican-complains-christmas-canceled>

15 <https://www.vaticannews.va/en/vatican-city/news/2021-11/holy-see-christmas-discrimination-european-union-inclusion.html>

16 <https://www.npr.org/sections/pictureshow/2022/04/12/1092036369/photos-kyiv-suburbs-continue-to-recover-bodies-after-russias-occupation-ends?t=1653490875794>

17 <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2021/dec/24/tagging-migrants-likely-to-be-another-failed-plan-to-stop-channel-crossings>

18 <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2021/nov/18/one-year-old-syrian-child-dies-in-forest-on-poland-belarus-border>

19 <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-england-manchester-59348873>

20 <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/11/26/channel-refugee-tragedy-tests-fragile-french-uk-ties-fuels-fears>

21 <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/europe/3-mosques-in-france-face-islamophobic-attack/2414458>

22 <https://www.theargus.co.uk/news/national/19673210.barry-bennell-quite-clearly-role-manchester-city-judge-told/>

23 <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/french-interior-minister-cancels-meeting-with-uk-counterpart-french-media-2021-11-26/>

24 <https://www.theguardian.com/law/2021/dec/19/human-rights-are-being-attacked-by-the-government-not-fine-tuned>

25 <https://www.dailyadvent.com/gb/tag/john-robinson>

26 <https://www.dailyadvent.com/gb/tag/nick-moss>

27 <https://www.cccb.ca/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/184-902.pdf>

how the Church decried the unconstitutionality of certain antivirus restrictions.²⁸ Today one of the few subjects on which we all seem to agree is the need for peace and justice. Why our agreement for justice leads to war, to crisis, to injustice? Why church and state, agreeing on peace and justice, don't get the concurrence? Maybe our agreement is only seeming. Why?

May be we don't remember that we're conscious.

May be we don't actually see and listen to.

Why then will you not admit the universe to be a conscious intelligence since conscious intelligences are born from it?—Cicero, De Natura Deorum.²⁹

The world faces the war and pandemic of human rights abuses regarding the right to liberty and security (article 5), the right to a fair trial (article 6), the right to respect for private and family life (article 8), freedom of thought, conscience and religion (article 9), freedom of expression (article 10), freedom of assembly and association (article 11).

Many of us ask questions, but do not want answers. We all are concerned with Peace and bringing about Justice/Law Reforms, Changing, including speeding up digitalisation/robotisation of Justice Systems. Peace, Reforms/Changings which are advocated all over the world at the present time do not bring about a fundamental change. In a corrupt society, such as this one, where we live and practice, there must be fundamental changes in the very structure of society. Any aspect of human rights law that inconveniences the modern governments is at risk. We agree with Martha Spurrier, John Robinson, that modern governments are constructing for itself a legislative armoury that is intended to be a "rewriting of the rules so only the government can win".³⁰ There is a flaw in the European convention on human rights. International human rights law recognises that few rights are absolute and reasonable limits may be placed on most rights and freedoms.³¹

Variously, they are subject to exceptions that are necessary in a democratic society in the interests of national security, public safety or the economic wellbeing of the country, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others.³²

The universalism invoked in the name of human rights is empty as manifested in the ECHR, insofar as those rights associated with peace, justice, free association, freedom of conscience etc are not absolute rights, but gifts of the state. The lesson to be drawn is that we only get what we fight for, and the struggle to defend and extend our rights has to be conducted by judges/lawyers/politicians, by ourselves.

Few judges/lawyers/politicians seem to dream in the modern age. And that is to Peace's\Justice's detriment. Maintaining that society was ultimately the product of the interactions of individuals, J. Krishnamurti³³ held that fundamental change in society could emerge only through freely undertaken radical change in the individual.³⁴

In this paper we are actually not answering the questions but rather exploring the questions. We share the Jiddu Krishnamurti's words: "In investigating the question we will

28 Mikhail Antonov, Russian Symphonia vs. Rule of Law?, 46 BYU L. Rev. 1183 (2021), 1208.

Available at: <https://digitalcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol46/iss5/7>

29 Cicero (1972) p. 132

30 <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2021/dec/14/human-rights-abuses-law-dominic-raab-judges>

31 <https://www.ag.gov.au/rights-and-protections/human-rights-and-anti-discrimination/human-rights-scrutiny/public-sector-guidance-sheets/absolute-rights>

32 <https://www.crossborderdataforum.org/governing-for-privacy-and-other-democratic-goals/>

33 Jiddu Krishnamurti (1895 – 1986) was a philosopher, speaker and writer. His interests included psychological revolution, the nature of mind, meditation, inquiry, human relationships, and bringing about radical change in society. He stressed the need for a revolution in the psyche of every human being and emphasised that such revolution cannot be brought about by any external entity, be it religious, political, or social.

34 Krishnamurti J. In the Problem is the Solution: Question and Answer Meetings in India. Chennai: Krishnamurti Foundation (2008) . Quoted in: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3673342/>

find the answer. The answer is in the problem. The meaning of that word 'problem' is, something thrown at you, a challenge - a question is a challenge. And whether we respond accurately to the challenge depends on the state of our minds, the capacity of our brains. Most of us, if I may respectfully point out, are more or less asleep.”³⁵ G.Gurdjieff³⁶ tells the same thing: a man “lives in sleep... He is a machine. He cannot stop the flow of his thoughts, he cannot control his imagination, his emotions, his attention”.³⁷

Are we really willing to change our minds, to let ourselves be questioned?

If we are not willing to change our minds, to let ourselves be questioned, to change our ways of acting, we will question everything, but we will never question ourselves and we will never have Peace and achieve Justice. To get Peace and Justice is to question oneself.

We can have Peace and achieve Justice only if we listen to the Higher Consciousness. Many times, we multiply the questions because we don't want to answer, that is, we don't want to change our opinion. We can accept the Higher Consciousness's power, only if we want to change. If we don't will, there is Higher Consciousness's silence (Peace\Justice's silence).

Nothingness. These days the autobiography³⁸ of former CJI Ranjan Gogoi³⁹ is very discussable,⁴⁰ generating a lot of heat and controversy on social media/among lawyers/judges.⁴¹ “Justice for the Judge”, Injustice for Everyone Else;- the mass media says.⁴²

In our opinion, for judges/lawyers/politicians/us, what is essential is not to take one's place on either side of Peace, Justice or War, Injustice, but rather to surpass both, and embrace, neither Light nor Dark, but Void and Nothingness. “Nothing is higher than heaven; nothing is beyond the walls of the world; nothing is lower than hell, or more,”- John D. Barrow⁴³ says.

Nothingness is an awe-inspiring, largely undigested concept that many regard with anxiety, nausea and panic — that's according to the Encyclopaedia of Philosophy.⁴⁴ But as John D. Barrow explains in his lecture⁴⁵, once you invent a handy symbol for this nothingness and learn how to calculate with it, it can turn into something friendly and incredibly useful. Philosophical thought holds that the void does not fall within the field of philosophical investigation and leaves it to the studies of physics which, reinterpreting matter as a force and void as a "potentially active" field, has completely abandoned the ancient conception

35 <https://jkrishnamurti.org/content/2nd-question-answer-meeting-32>

36 George Ivanovich Gurdjieff (1866-1877 – 1949) was a Russian philosopher, mystic, spiritual teacher, and composer of Armenian and Greek descent, born in Alexandropol, Russian Empire. Gurdjieff taught that most humans do not possess a unified consciousness and thus live their lives in a state of hypnotic "waking sleep", but that it is possible to awaken to a higher state of consciousness and achieve full human potential. Gurdjieff described a method attempting to do so, calling the discipline "The Work" (connoting "work on oneself") or "the System". According to his principles and instructions, Gurdjieff's method for awakening one's consciousness unites the methods of the fakir, monk and yogi, and thus he referred to it as the "Fourth Way".

37 http://maaber.50megs.com/issue_june05/spiritual_traditions1e.htm

38 Ranjan Gogoi, JUSTICE FOR THE JUDGE: AN AUTOBIOGRAPHY (2021)

39 Ranjan Gogoi (1954) is a former Indian Judge of the Supreme Court of India

40 <https://www.barandbench.com/columns/judging-a-book-by-its-sealed-cover-a-preview-of-ranjan-gogois-justice-for-the-judge>

41 <https://www.barandbench.com/columns/judging-a-book-by-its-sealed-cover-a-preview-of-ranjan-gogois-justice-for-the-judge> ; <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/shouldnt-have-been-on-bench-that-heard-harassment-charge-gogoi-101638993709336.html> ; <https://www.livelaw.in/columns/ranjan-gogoi-memoir-justice-for-judge-chief-justice-of-india-supreme-court-187414> ; <https://www.barandbench.com/columns/judging-a-book-by-its-sealed-cover-a-preview-of-ranjan-gogois-justice-for-the-judge>.

42 <https://thewire.in/law/justice-for-the-judge-injustice-for-everyone-else>

43 John David Barrow FRS (1952 – 2020) was an English cosmologist, theoretical physicist, and mathematician.

44 <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/nothingness/>

45 <https://plus.maths.org/content/john-barrow-zero-hero>

of the void. Heinz Rudolf Pagels⁴⁶ explains: “The old idea of emptiness, which assimilated it to pure space, to nothingness, has also changed. After having created, in the thirties and forties, the relativistic quantum theory of fields, physicists ceased to conceive the vacuum in the traditional terms. In reality the vacuum, the space are made of particles and antiparticles that spontaneously create and annihilate themselves”.⁴⁷ Indeed, according to Quantum field theory (QFT) the "physical" void does not mean the absence of being, the non-being of the ellies, but it is a potentially active reality, in the sense that it is a void that lives and fits into the continuous process of creation and destruction of matter. John D. Barrow writes that gradually, this exotic new picture of quantum nothingness succumbed to experimental exploration in the form of vacuum tubes, light bulbs and X-rays. Now the 'empty' space itself started to be probed. There was always something left: a vacuum energy that permeated every fibre of the Universe.⁴⁸

Emptiness, unlike "nothingness", is a state of mind. In the paper titled “Civil Justice, Discretion, Consciousness etc”⁴⁹ we’ve already applied Emptiness to Justice.⁵⁰ Here we're seeking to make it clear that the Void like other elements Earth, Fire, Air and Water⁵¹ has a great importance to explore Peace and Justice. In emptiness we find, in compressed form, *inter alia*, Higher Consciousness’s vision, and the secret of Peace and Justice. The pages have been intentionally left blank by Higher Consciousness; the blank pages seem to have the knowledge of the secret of the Void or Zero (Emptiness). The elusiveness of the blank pages points out that there can be no conclusive answer to unravel the mystery of Justice. In martial arts, the power of the Void is invoked frequently, to connect to the intrinsic creative energy.⁵²

J. Krishnamurti says beauty: “Emptiness comes as a sunset comes of an evening,” - and he explains- “That emptiness of the mind cannot be produced: the mind cannot be made empty, cannot be put together to be empty. That emptiness comes as a sunset comes of an evening, full of beauty, enchantment, and richness; that comes as naturally as the blossoming of a flower when there is no fear, when there are no escapes, when there is no boredom, and when there is no seeking. And, that is the most important of all - there must be no seeking. Because, you cannot find; you cannot find the everlasting. That which is beyond time you cannot search out. It may come to you but you cannot go to it because your minds are too shallow, petty, empty, full of ambition, fears, ugliness, and distortion. Therefore, the mind must empty itself - not because it wants that. Because, when you want that, you have a motive and, the moment you have a motive, you have lost your energy. Therefore, it is only the mind that is completely empty that is in a state of inaction. That inaction is action. And, it is only such a mind that is being passionate; it is only such a mind that can live with beauty and not get used to beauty - the beauty of a tree, the beauty of a face, the beauty of an eye, of a smile, of the ugly, dirty road, the squalor, the dirt, the poverty, it is only the passionate mind that can live with it and not get distorted. And it is only such a mind that is so completely empty that is in a state of meditation.”⁵³

No doubt, if judges/lawyers/politicians/everyone of us get attuned to the powers of the void, Peace and Justice can be achieved.

46 Heinz Rudolf Pagels (1939 – 1988) was an American physicist, an associate professor of physics at Rockefeller University, the executive director and chief executive officer of the New York Academy of Sciences, and president of the International League for Human Rights. He wrote the popular science books *The Cosmic Code* (1982), *Perfect Symmetry* (1985), and *The Dreams of Reason: The Computer and the Rise of the Sciences of Complexity* (1988).

47 Heinz Rudolf Pagels, *The cosmic code*, ed. Bollate Boringhieri, Turin (1994) chapter 21, 257

48 John D. Barrow, *The Book of Nothing* (2009), chapter nought "Nothingology—Flying to Nowhere"

<https://quotepark.com/quotes/1926315-john-d-barrow-the-quantum-revolution-showed-us-why-the-old-pictu/>

49 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

50 Ibid

51 See more: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wuxing_\(Chinese_philosophy\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wuxing_(Chinese_philosophy))

52 <https://naturemartialarts.com/void/>

53 J. Krishnamurti, *Collected Works*, Vol. XIV, 118

Whether we agree with it or not, or understand it or not, Peace\Justice is a vision, dream, grasped at the moment of waking and the edge of consciousness. That dream is of a gnostic transformation within judge/lawyer/politician/the individual, and changing collective spirit and circumstance within the world.

And we are together, answering the questions, or rather investigating the questions. The investigation or the exploration into the question depends on how we approach the question, how we approach any problem in life, whether it is a justice or peace case, a business problem, a deeply emotional problem, problem of truth, and so on. When we stand close to the question, almost touch it, feel it, then perhaps out of that question one finds the true answer.

So if we may proceed with the questions.

Why our agreement for peace and justice leads to war, crisis, to injustice? Why church and state, agreeing on peace and justice, don't get the concurrence? Maybe our agreement is only seeming. Why?

Because we've missed.

We've missed Liberty. We've got a Hobson's choice.⁵⁴ We've got the King Ideology. If we have no Love, we have no peace, we have no justice. Love would give us Peace and Justice.

Giordano Bruno⁵⁵ said "that one unique force, Love, that unites infinite worlds and renders them alive."⁵⁶ The Neapolitan philosopher had intuited what is the fundamental nature of reality, as exactly the physicist Federico Faggin⁵⁷ has experienced.⁵⁸ In fact, Faggin's theory has an experimental basis and it constitutes a real revolution. In this passage he tells us how the units of consciousness⁵⁹ that emerge from the basic quantum field combine with each other.⁶⁰ It occurs through cycles of perception, understanding, and action, in which these units self-organize into successive and richer levels, into the Whole that is more than the sum of the parts. It is worth considering that the internal structure can be described with external symbols, but there is a meaning that remains ungraspable and cannot be translated into symbols.

54 <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/Hobson%27s%20choice>

55 Giordano Bruno (born Filippo Bruno, 1548 – 1600) was an Italian Dominican friar, philosopher, mathematician, poet, cosmological theorist, and Hermetic occultist. He is known for his cosmological theories, which conceptually extended the then-novel Copernican model.

56 Quoted in Carlo Dorofatti, *Soul & Reality - Metaphysics, Magic and Inner Search for a New Era of Awareness* (2011) 281

57 Federico Faggin (1941) is an Italian-American physicist, engineer, inventor and entrepreneur. He is best known for designing the first commercial microprocessor, the Intel 4004. He led the 4004 (MCS-4) project and the design group during the first five years of Intel's microprocessor effort. Faggin also created, while working at Fairchild Semiconductor in 1968, the self-aligned MOS (metal-oxide-semiconductor) silicon-gate technology (SGT), which made possible MOS semiconductor memory chips, CCD image sensors, and the microprocessor. After the 4004, he led development of the Intel 8008 and 8080, using his SGT methodology for random logic chip design, which was essential to the creation of early Intel microprocessors. He was co-founder (with Ralph Ungermann) and CEO of Zilog, the first company solely dedicated to microprocessors, and led the development of the Zilog Z80 and Z8 processors. He was later the co-founder and CEO of Cygnit Technologies, and then Synaptics.

In 2010, he received the 2009 National Medal of Technology and Innovation, the highest honor the United States confers for achievements related to technological progress. In 2011, Faggin founded the Federico and Elvia Faggin Foundation to support the scientific study of consciousness at US universities and research institutes. In 2015, the Faggin Foundation helped to establish a \$1 million endowment for the Faggin Family Presidential Chair in the Physics of Information at UC Santa Cruz to promote the study of "fundamental questions at the interface of physics and related fields including mathematics, complex systems, biophysics, and cognitive science, with the unifying theme of information in physics.". Federico Faggin has been a Silicon Valley resident since 1968 and is a naturalized US citizen.

58 <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-fundamental-nature-of-reality/>

59 <https://wsimag.com/science-and-technology/64789-one-and-the-consciousness-units>

60 Ibid

Symbols differ with regard to their meaning and their cultural context. Symbols do not have the same impact, and sometimes the same meaning, depending on the cultural context in which they are displayed. The hijab is in its own cultural context in Turkey. The crucifix is in its own cultural context in Italy. This is not the same as an Islamic headscarf's cultural context in Switzerland, in France, in Italy etc or a crucifix cultural context out of Italy. The context of the display, especially cultural context, helps determine the strength of an external religious symbol: the impact of the public display of an Islamic head scarf definitely varies according to the circumstances. It is a more powerful external symbol in Turkey than in France.

In France the head scarf's impact was too limited to restrict the rights invoked.

Dahlab has several special aspects:

First of all, prohibitions against wearing religious signs or clothes constitute an interference with the individual freedom to manifest one's beliefs because the person is prevented from acting in conformity with his beliefs. It was for the Court to determine the compatibility of this interference with the Convention.

Conversely, in France in case of the Muslim women's coverings, nobody was prevented from acting, nor was anyone forced to act, besides Muslims women themselves. Strictly speaking, Muslim women did not have to justify any co-action (coercion), or any infringement of the French's internal or external liberty. There was no violation of the Frenchmen's external liberty, because the French were not forced to act against their conscience. Nor were they prevented from acting in conformity with their conscience. Nor were the pupils at school, the students at Universities prevented from believing anything. They were not indoctrinated and did not suffer from any proselytism.

Even if ECtHR could perceive the France's apprehension, the Court wouldn't support the interference by the State concerning the rights at issue. Here neither the subjective perception nor emotional disturbance of France regarding Muslim women's coverings don't matter.

Let's return to a battle around the crucifix in classroom in Italy in the *Lautsi v Italy* case.⁶¹ Here the Grand Chamber went further. Although the Court perceived the applicant's apprehension, it nevertheless rejected the applicant's argument: "Be that as it may, the applicant's subjective perception is not in itself sufficient to establish a breach of Article 2 of Protocol No. 1".⁶² But the judges' subjective perception is in itself sufficient? It seems that Yes. The judges of Grand Chamber rejected the Second Section's argument that the display of the crucifix resulted in the *emotional disturbance*.⁶³ The Grand Chamber reasoned that emotional disturbance is only a *subjective perception*, which is not in itself sufficient to establish a breach of Article 2 of Protocol 1.⁶⁴ The Convention does not protect subjective perceptions.

This simple statement was sufficient to conclude that there was no infringement of the rights at issue. This statement would be sufficient to conclude that in France Muslim women wearing the coverings don't infringe of the rights at issue.

The slight impact of the crucifix and of Muslim women coverings is the real *ratio decidendi*. We agree with the Court. The Convention does not require any confessional neutrality, the presence of constraint exercised by a State on Muslim women would suffice to conclude there is violation of Article 9.⁶⁵

As the crucifix in Italy so the hijab in France is *an essentially passive symbol*. Theoretically, a teacher wearing a kippa could teach pupils wearing veils and turbans in a classroom that has a crucifix mounted on the blackboard.

61 More details: Zucca Lorenzo, *Lautsi: A Commentary on a decision by the ECtHR Grand Chamber*, International Journal of Constitutional Law, Volume 11, Issue 1, 218–229 (January 2013) <https://doi.org/10.1093/icon/mos008>

62 Puppink Grégor, *Opt. cit.*, 902

63 *Ibid*

64 *Ibid*

65 Puppink Grégor, *Opt. cit.*, 904

The concept of a *passive symbol* was developed by the Italian Government in its argument in *Lautsi v Italy* case. It was done not in order to denigrate the crucifix. The Government explained that the symbol was passive, because it did not require any action, prayer, or reverence from those who view it.⁶⁶ It does not mean that the meaning of the crucifix is insignificant. This is also how the Grand Chamber understood the crucifix's character: the crucifix is passive.⁶⁷

A *weak external symbol* may be a religious covering worn by Muslim women—such as hijab, niqab or burka—the impact of which is weak on other people. In addition of being a weak external symbol, such religious covering is also a passive symbol because it requires no action on the part of others. On the other hand, practically in every state Themis could be an example of an active symbol because it represents the justice and (sometimes) requires those who is in a courtroom to stand up.

We share the idea that the concept of a *passive symbol* is not contradictory with that of *powerful external symbols*, although it is often affirmed that such is the case. The concept of a passive symbol is opposite to that of an *active symbol*, while a *powerful external symbol* is opposite to a *weak external symbol*.

The globalization as well as the present disintegration of societies, witnessed especially in Western countries that intensifies the crisis of collective identities, put a brake on the individualist liberalism that supports the modern concept of freedom. From this perspective, the plea of the Italian government in *Lautsi* in favor of the crucifix as a fundamental symbol of the civilization reveals all its value. Italy, while resolutely desiring to respect individual liberties, refused to renounce to one of its main traditional symbol in the name of the postmodern cultural relativism and nihilism. Italian Ambassador Sergio Busetto expressed it as follows: “respecting the religious identity of an individual must be possible while respecting the religious identity of the society in which he lives”.⁶⁸ Here we have to strengthen legal and political sciences themselves, while sharing the often-voiced concern about ECtHR, its role in the contracting states.

The judgments of the Court are not directly enforceable. Thus, the authority of the Court is based on the assent of the States and, perhaps even more, on its prestige. Because of the intergovernmental nature of the Court, the execution of judgments comes under the competence of the national authorities, under the supervision of the other governments. States execute the judgments with, more or less, docility and goodwill according to the circumstances. The reaction to the *Lautsi* judgment freed many judicial/political and religious authorities to speak out against what has often been perceived as an unacceptable ideological abuse of the Court.

In the *Lautsi* case, it was obvious that the present Italian government would have refused to submit to a decision to withdraw crucifixes. Even more serious for the authority of the Court, this refusal would have been supported by numerous governments. Finally, it seems that for the Court, the present crisis in Europe make it impossible to maintain both a unanimously appreciated prestige and *progressive* judicial activism.

In the famous judgment of *Leyla Sahin*, the Grand Chamber ECtHR affirmed that “[w]here questions concerning the relationship between State and religions are at stake, on which opinion in a democratic society may reasonably differ widely, the role of the national decision-making body must be given special importance.”⁶⁹

This choice pertaining to the religious aspect of the common good is ultimately a fundamental choice, and the European Court must abstain from making it. Those who want the European Court to overstep its jurisdiction to exercise such a choice, in fact—in a

66 *Lautsi*, 2011 Eur. Ct. H.R. § 36.

67 *Ibid.* § 72.

68 Busetto Sergio, Ambassador of Italy, Opening speech of the symposium organised by the ECLJ, the CNR and the Italian Embassy, at the Council of Europe (Apr. 30 2010) available at https://classic.iclrs.org/content/blurb/files/ARTICLE_LAUTSI_PUPPINCK_English_BYU_Law_Review.pdf

69 *Leyla Şahin v. Turkey*, App. 44774/98, 2005 Eur. Ct. H.R. § 109.

very medieval way— long to see it set up as a new spiritual authority above the States: a theocracy of the atheistic religion of human rights. In their defense, it is true that the absorption of morality, spirituality and religiosity by human rights transforms the European Court into a *conscience of Europe*.⁷⁰ Thus, the Court becomes the functional equivalent of an ultimate oracle of a new magisterium, which specifically applies directly to States, not only in civil matters but also in moral, spiritual and religious matters. This magisterium also imposes its positions upon individual consciences because of its great prestige. In fact, as any society naturally has a religious/spiritual dimension, a society which claims to be purely secular can only capture the totality of spiritual power by transforming the political ideology which rules it into religion.

The Grand Chamber did not choose to implicate such matters, unlike the Second Section's judgment.⁷¹

In addition, this distinction between signs and symbols, according to whether they are powerful or weak, passive or active, will probably be useful below to distinguish other situations.

Symbols are a language of allegory, created long before the lettered words we are imprisoned by today. "A picture tells a thousand words"⁷². Combined with oral tradition, symbols are just as effective at containing and recalling information as any computer – possibly more so.

Thus the consciousness of incompleteness is created which is the stimulus to move forward in understanding, and which manifests itself in us as an innate need. Between two Units that collaborate in this knowledge, a kind of empathy is created, which leads to working together to understand and to know each other better and which can reach the maximum mutual understanding, a kind of common self-knowledge that determines the birth of a new Unit with the aim to deepen common self-knowledge, the thing that can happen since the meaning has infinite depth. This new Unit is of a higher hierarchical level. New Unit will try to relate to another self at his own level of understanding to increase common self-knowledge, creating the next hierarchical level.

New symbols are created in a process, that will lead to the discovery of all possible common knowledge. From here it will be possible to start a new leap in the plan with new symbols that will lead to the formation of an ever-growing vocabulary of an universal language of which selves, belonging to a given hierarchical level, can understand all the symbols of the lower hierarchical levels, but those of the higher levels only partially. In this way we know the holistic structure of the real which describes the irreducible semantic-symbolic nature of "One". It is worth emphasizing that the concepts of space, time and quantum fields are the physical reality of which all that is possible can be measured. Here we refer to Ukhtomsky⁷³'s concept, too. From his point of view, activity is always directed towards some kind of goals in the future, and it's success depends on the depth of comprehending reality, as gained through the whole of our past experience, the whole developmental history of the personality, and the biological inheritance history of the species. This adequacy and depth of understanding are, in turn, determined by our ability to constantly renounce our own prejudice and egoism, to look at reality as it is with empathic attentiveness. This is especially important in the social sphere, in justice, and particularly in interpersonal relationships, where the reality we encounter is the Personality of Another man. The leitmotiv and pathos of Ukhtomsky's concept lies in the Dominant

70 As the Court presents itself in the book celebrating its fiftieth anniversary, *THE CONSCIENCE OF EUROPE: 50 YEARS OF THE EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS* (Jonathan Sharpe ed. 2011)

71 *The Case of Lautsi v. Italy: A Synthesis*

72 Henrik Ibsen, a Norwegian playwright and theatre director, first said "A thousand words leave not the same deep impression as does a single deed." After his death in 1906 this quote was plagiarized and para-phrased into what we know now.

73 Alexei Alexeyevich Ukhtomsky (1875 – 1942) was a Russian and Soviet physiologist. His main contribution to science was the theory of dominant.

facing the personality of another.⁷⁴ “There is no such force, even within “positive science”, that could free man from the burden of moral freedom,”⁷⁵ - Alexey Ukhtomsky confirmed. Should we talk not of justice but of love, empathy, the Unit. J.Krishnamurti teaches us: “So do we know the quality of mercy, peace, justice - mercy, love and compassion? If that doesn't exist there is no justice. Compassion has its own intelligence, not the intelligence of a clever mind, of a clever brain.”⁷⁶ So to comprehend we could find out whether one is capable to love, not seek justice. “If you love your community, then you need to be insisting on justice in all circumstances,”⁷⁷ — Bryan Stevenson is sure. And we agree. In the paper titled “Social Values in Europe etc”⁷⁸ we've concluded on the correlance between justice, love and honesty of the mind.

If we have no justice\peace, we have no freedom. Justice and Peace should give us liberty, liberty from any evil, first of all.

Liberty is our most basic right. Article 5 ECHR protects our right to liberty and security⁷⁹. The ordinary citizen looks to the courts as the only resort for protect their liberty: equal justice is to protect liberty. Peace, Liberty, Equality, Justice. These words represent basic values of democratic political systems. Democratic values support the belief that an orderly society can exist in which freedom is preserved. But order and freedom must be balanced. Also a court should have liberty. Judicial independence⁸⁰ does, however, mean that judges must be free to exercise their judicial powers without interference from litigants, the State, the media or powerful individuals or entities.

In the paper titled “Civil Justice. Discretion. etc”⁸¹ we've already studied the judicial independence with the conclusion that the appearance of the judicial law-making is feasible. It should be *elegantia juris*. The primary sources of law (creative precedents) and the secondary sources of law (precedents of interpretation, habits of judicial practice and even “quasi-normative” judicial acts – acts of normative interpretation) should be resulted from that appearance.⁸²

Peace, justice, equality and fraternity⁸³ are the values that guided our liberty. “In comparison with liberty and equality, the idea of fraternity has had a lesser place in democratic theory. It is thought to be less specifically a political concept, not in itself defining any of the democratic rights ...”⁸⁴. This observation, formulated by John Rawls in his ‘A Theory of Justice’, will occur to anyone who examines the Republican triad: political philosophy is very much concerned with liberty and equality, but considerably less so with fraternity.⁸⁵

74 See more: <http://www.nadin.ws/ante-study/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/Zueva-Zuev-Dominance-Concept-by-A.A.-Ukhtomsky.pdf>

75 Quoted in: <http://www.nadin.ws/ante-study/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/Zueva-Zuev-Dominance-Concept-by-A.A.-Ukhtomsky.pdf>

76 <https://jkrishnamurti.org/content/2nd-question-answer-meeting-32>

77 <https://quotefancy.com/quote/1622354/Bryan-Stevenson-If-you-love-your-community-then-you-need-to-be-insisting-on-justice-in>

78 Olga Nickole Papkova Kuyan. Social Values in Europe. Protecting Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Religion, Creating What?: Justice, Sophia, Phronesis. Authorea. July 14, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.162626095.53333722/v1.

79 <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/human-rights-act/article-5-right-liberty-and-security>

80 <https://www.britannica.com/topic/judicial-independence>

81 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

82 Ibid

83 About this topic see Marco Martino, “La prospettiva della fraternità nel pensiero di John Rawls,” Nuova Umanità XXXII (2010): 549–566. Starting from Rawls’ principle of difference, Francesco Viola proposes the concept of “similitude” as an interpretation of fraternity: “La fraternità nel bene commune,” in Lila B. Archideo, ed., Epistemologia de las ciencias sociales: La fraternidad, Centro de Investigaciones en Antropología Filos’fica y Cultural (Buenos Aires: CIAFIC Ediciones, 2004)

84 Rawls John, A Theory of Justice (1971) 105

85 Always somewhat eclipsed by the other two values, fraternity has undergone neither the formal treatment initially generated by Berlin’s distinction between “positive” and “negative” liberty, nor the analytical effort to define the term similar to Williams’, Nagel’s, or Dworkin’s approach to equality.

In comparison to the Human Justice, the Divine Justice⁸⁶ turns to the fraternity.⁸⁷

We argue that attempts to achieve justice and the regulation of business faltered not because of the fraternity absence or presence among the values or the differences between human and divine justice, but because of the King Ideology we serve.

The true evil of peace\justice and liberty is the ideology that we created — that there are people less/more deserving, less/more worthy, less/more human, less/more evolved.

If everybody understands that's the true problem of peace\justice, then it becomes easier to understand how we don't really get justice with any justice/law reforms. Because we never deal with the ideology. And everyone is implicated in this story. Everyone is implicated in this moment that we live in where the smog created by our history of war and injustice is still in the air. Few of us are breathing the prana⁸⁸, many of us are breathing the air of Ideology and serve the King Ideology and it's corrupting our world view, just like it corrupted the world view of people before us.

The great performance of 2020⁸⁹2021 is the new *Kulturkampf*⁹⁰ and its new nice play in 2022⁹¹.

It's a radically new phase that enriches the traditional Western fight against war with fundamental themes. The clash between Europe and Russian Ideology⁹², between Europe and an accomplished Islamic⁹³ ideology takes place at the same time on all levels: geopolitical, energetic, on the secular or religious nature of the state, cultural and jihadist penetration.

Future of any European State will be the same for a *civilization* reason: Afro-Turkish-Arab Islamic immigration, when it exceeds a certain percentage, can no longer be integrated, because at a certain point, the number becomes a force, and the countries of origin of

86 <https://www.quoteskosmos.com/bible/bible-verses/Fraternity.html>

87 https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/letters/2021/documents/papa-francesco_20210521_lettera-card-turkson.html ; https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/travels/2019/outside/documents/papa-francesco_20190204_documento-fratellanza-umana.html ; <https://via.library.depaul.edu/vhj/vol30/iss1/4/> etc.

88 Prana (the Sanskrit word for breath, "life force", or "vital principle") permeates reality on all levels including inanimate objects.

89 *Kulturkampf* (culture struggle) was the conflict that took place from 1872 to 1878 between the government of the Kingdom of Prussia led by Otto von Bismarck and the Roman Catholic Church led by Pope Pius IX. The main issues were clerical control of education and ecclesiastical appointments. A unique feature of *Kulturkampf* compared to other struggles between the state and the Catholic Church in other countries was its anti-Polish component. (Smith Helmut Walser , ed., The Oxford Handbook of Modern German History, 360 (2011) By analogy, the term *Kulturkampf* is sometime used to describe any conflict between secular and religious authorities or deeply opposing values, beliefs between sizable factions within a nation, community, or other group.)"Kulturkampf – Definition, meaning & more – Collins Dictionary". Retrieved 21 December 2016.)

90 *Kulturkampf* (culture struggle) was the conflict that took place from 1872 to 1878 between the government of the Kingdom of Prussia led by Otto von Bismarck and the Roman Catholic Church led by Pope Pius IX. The main issues were clerical control of education and ecclesiastical appointments. A unique feature of *Kulturkampf* compared to other struggles between the state and the Catholic Church in other countries was its anti-Polish component. (Smith Helmut Walser , ed., The Oxford Handbook of Modern German History, 360 (2011) By analogy, the term *Kulturkampf* is sometime used to describe any conflict between secular and religious authorities or deeply opposing values, beliefs between sizable factions within a nation, community, or other group.)"Kulturkampf – Definition, meaning & more – Collins Dictionary". Retrieved 21 December 2016.)

91 <https://www.iipvienna.com/new-blog/2022/5/19/der-russland-ukraine-krieg-und-ein-neuer-kulturkampf>

92 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russia_under_Vladimir_Putin

93 There are the two main sects within Islam: Sunni and Shia. Today, about 85 percent of the approximately 1.6 billion Muslims around the world are Sunni, while 15 percent are Shia, according to an estimate by the Council on Foreign Relations. Sunni Islam is separated into four main schools of jurisprudence, namely, Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi'i, Hanbali. Shia Islam, on the other hand, is separated into three major sects: Twelvers, Ismailis, and Zaydis. Though Sunni and Shia agree on most of the fundamental beliefs and practices of Islam, a bitter split between the two goes back some 14 centuries. The divide originated with a dispute over who should succeed the Prophet Muhammad as leader of the Islamic faith he introduced.

In recent years, Sunni–Shia relations have been increasingly marked by conflict, particularly the Iran–Saudi Arabia proxy conflict. Sectarian violence persists to this day from Pakistan to Yemen and is a major element of friction throughout the Middle East and South Asia.

these new immigrants are increasingly intolerant Islamic countries where hatred towards the Jew, the Christian-Crusader, the Atheist or the apostate is taught in flies and also in national education because it is based on the Sharia.

VI Soloviev also spoke about the stubborn and exhausting struggle that some European states will have to endure against the awakened Islam.⁹⁴

Alexandre del Valle⁹⁵ says: "It is enough to be over 50 years old to observe how the Islamic world is much more contaminated by the radical Islamist virus now than in the 1980s.

Thirty years later, the Islamist virus multiplied in Europe, it is accompanied by the uncontrolled Islamic immigration that every day brings to Europe hundreds of thousands of young Muslims whom the fundamentalist Islamist organizations know very well to train and fanatize".⁹⁶ And now we agree that the 'Islamic State' will benefit from the Ukraine war.⁹⁷

In 1993 Samuel P. Huntington said: «It is my hypothesis that the fundamental source of conflict in this new world will not be primarily ideological or primarily economic. The great divisions among humankind and the dominating source of conflict will be cultural. Nation states will remain the most powerful actors in world affairs, but the principal conflicts of global politics will occur between nations and groups of different civilizations. The clash of civilizations will be the battle lines of the future".⁹⁸

Now the scholars give support to the clash-of-civilizations hypothesis.⁹⁹ Olivier Roy says on Ukraine and the Clash of Civilisation theory. The today crisis isn't a clash with the religiosity.¹⁰⁰ The France-Turkey epicenter was in France, where almost 15 percent say they are atheist¹⁰¹ and in which almost one in 10 people are immigrants. It's a clash of two faces. The face of Turkey has a reality of Erdogan, the *national-Islamist*, pan-turkish¹⁰²

94 Solovjov Vladimir (Author) Thomas R. Beyer (Editor), Alexander Bakshy (Translator), Czesław Miłosz (Introduction), Stephan Hoeller (Afterword), War, Progress, and the End of History: Three Conversations: Including a Short Tale of the Antichrist (Esalen-Lindisfarne Library of Russian Philosophy)

<http://www.vehi.net/soloviev/trirazgov/razgovor1.html>

95 Marc d'Anna (1968), writing under the pen name Alexandre del Valle, is a Franco-Italian writer, professor, columnist, and political commentator. He is known primarily for his analysis of Islamic extremism, and his criticism of Erdoğan's neo-Ottoman, Islamist, and post-Kemalist Turkey. Del Valle is a proponent of the "PanWest paradigm"—the cooperation between the West and Russia against radical Islamism—and coined the concept of "Red-green-brown alliance" in 2002. His domains of interest focus on Islamic extremism, new geopolitical threats, civilizational conflicts, and terrorism, as well as Mediterranean issues such as Turkey's proposed accession to the European Union. Alexandre del Valle wrote on international relations and geopolitics of the Arab-Muslim world.

<https://www.alexandrevalle.com/single-post/2004/12/06/The-Reds-The-Browns-and-the-Greens-or-The-Convergence-of-Totalitarianisms>

96 <https://www.alexandrevalle.com/single-post/2002/09/06/islamist-totalitarianism-democracies-under-attack-english-summary>

97 <https://www.dw.com/en/the-islamic-state-benefits-from-ukraine-war/a-61827617>

98 Huntington Samuel P, The Clash of Civilizations?, Foreign Affairs, 72:3, 22-49 (Summer 1993),

<https://www2.kenyon.edu/Depts/Religion/Fac/Adler/Politics/Huntington-Clash.htm>

99 The Clash of Civilizations is a thesis that people's cultural and religious identities will be the primary source of conflict in the post-Cold War world. The American political scientist Samuel P. Huntington argued that future wars would be fought not between countries, but between cultures. It was proposed in a 1992 lecture at the American Enterprise Institute, which was then developed in a 1993 Foreign Affairs article titled *The Clash of Civilizations?*, (Official copy (free preview): The Clash of Civilizations?, Foreign Affairs (Summer 1993),

<https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/united-states/1993-06-01/clash-civilizations>) in response to his former student Francis Fukuyama's 1992 book, *The End of History and the Last Man*. Huntington later expanded his thesis in a 1996 book *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*. The phrase itself was earlier used from 1946.

100 <https://www.nouvelobs.com/guerre-en-ukraine/20220227.OBS55056/olivier-roy-la-guerre-en-ukraine-nous-prouve-que-la-theorie-du-choc-des-civilisations-ne-fonctionne-pas.html>

101 See above EVS overview

102 Pan-Turkism is an ideological nationalist movement that seeks to promote the union of all Turkish peoples, including - at least originally - also the Hungarians, linked to the Turanian ideology (widespread, even at an official level, in Hungary, Turkey and Japan), Pan-Turkism is a movement born in the late nineteenth century, spread between the Ottoman Empire, Austria-Hungary and Germany, and later spread also to the Russian Empire, particularly in the regions of Western Turkestan. The father of Pan-Turkism is considered the Hungarian orientalist Ármin Vámbéry. Ármin Vámbéry (Arminius Vámbéry) born Hermann Bamberger, also known as Ármin Bamberger; (1832-1913) was a Hungarian historian, linguist, orientalist and writer.

-neo-Ottoman¹⁰³ reality. The *face* of France has a reality of President Macron, the reality of democracy, liberty, secularism, human freedoms and rights. Masha Gessen names Putin the Man Without a Face.¹⁰⁴

Using World Values Surveys from 86 nations, some scientists examined differences between Christians and Muslims in preferences for religious political leaders.¹⁰⁵ The results suggested a marked difference between Muslims and Christians in their attitudes toward religious politicians, with Muslims more favorable by 20 points out of 100. Instead, the scholars found that a clash of individual beliefs—between the devout and the secular—along with enduring differences between the more developed and less developed world explains the difference between Islam and Christianity with regards to preferences for religious political leaders.¹⁰⁶

Hans Urs von Balthasar¹⁰⁷ said that “the greatest enigma that there is in man is that he is two things at the same time: a nature (that is, a spiritual soul incarnated in a body, an individual) and a person (incomparable, eternal uniqueness)”.¹⁰⁸ Men don't have two detached and distinct dimensions, but men have a magnificent integration of two friend areas that transform and elevate themselves.

The modern play of Russia or France arises not from the fact that one system of norms or one separate norm is *correct* and the other is not, but because these norms were formed within the framework of different cultures that were separated one from another. They remain different: a girl with a navel pierced - a student from Moscow State University or from the Parisian Sorbonne- and a girl in the burqa from the Afghan or Turkish wilderness. Globalization confronts them at the same place and the Ideology separates them.

The German chancellor, Angela Merkel said the idea of people from different cultural backgrounds living happily *side by side* did not work, the onus was on immigrants to do more to integrate into German society. She claimed the country's attempts to create a multicultural society have *utterly failed*. “This [multicultural] approach has failed, utterly failed”,- Merkel told at the meeting in Potsdam, west of Berlin, in 2010.¹⁰⁹

Gérard de Nerval¹¹⁰ wrote: “Free thinker! Do you think you are the only thinker on this earth in which life blazes inside all things? Your liberty does what it wishes with the powers it controls, but when you gather to plan, the universe is not there”.¹¹¹

103 On the neo-ottomanism see: Wastnidge Edward, Imperial Grandeur and Selective Memory: Re-assessing Neo-Ottomanism in Turkish Foreign and Domestic Politics. Middle East Critique. 28 (1): 7–28 (2 January 2019), <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/19436149.2018.1549232?journalCode=ccri20> ; LE RADICI DEL NEO-OTTOMANESIMO DI ERDOĞAN, <https://www.babilonmagazine.it/turchia-erdogan-neo-ottomanesimo/>

104 <https://www.amazon.it/Man-Without-Face-Unlikely-Vladimir/dp/1594488428>

105 Breznau Nate, LykClash Valerie, Kelley Jonathan, M. D. R. Evans, A of Civilizations? Preferences for Religious Political Leaders in 86 Nations, 2011, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1468-5906.2011.01605.x>

106 External link: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1468-5906.2011.01605.x/full>

107 Hans Urs von Balthasar (1905–1988) was a Swiss theologian and Catholic priest, unique among the great Central European theologians. He has produced a vast theological work, which can be considered among the most influential of the twentieth century and has since found many interpreters in contemporary theological research. His theology was influenced by his contacts with Jesuits, philosophers and theologians, such as Erich Przywara, Jean Daniélou and Henri de Lubac. With his activity as a lecturer and his numerous publications he contributed to a renewed interest in patristics, making it available again to theology and the Christian faith. Von Balthasar is considered among the greatest Catholic theologians of the twentieth century, together with Karl Rahner, Henri de Lubac, Romano Guardini and others.

108 On the issue see: Harrison Victoria S, Personal Identity And Integration: Von Balthasar's Phenomenology Of Human Holiness, The Heythrop Journal, 40(4):424 - 437 (December 2002)

109 <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2010/oct/17/angela-merkel-german-multiculturalism-failed>

110 Gérard Labrunie, known as Gérard de Nerval (1808-1855) is a French writer and poet. He is a major figure in French romanticism, he is best known for his poems and short stories, including his book Les Filles du feu, a collection of short stories (the most famous being Sylvie), his collection of sonnets (Les Chimères) published in 1854 and his new poetic Aurélia published in 1855.

111 Gérard de Nerval, Golden Lines (translator Robert Bly) (1854), <http://poemhunter.blogspot.com/2007/12/golden-lines.html>

Carlo Molari¹¹² said that “the universe is a system composed of other systems. They are complex, they continually adapt to their surroundings. We too are part of this constantly changing system of relationships”.¹¹³ Molari speaks of the *opportunities of time*, which must be seized with an open and available attitude, like an open door, in order to be able to welcome the elements that are most suitable for us. Men need to feel like citizens of the cosmos, which is the highest feeling, the one that generates a great force out of men and out towards the environment that surrounds men, of intense participation in the motion of life in which men are placed. Feeling this participation helps the establishment of harmonious relationships, the harmonious adaptation of the inside with the outside, helps the approach to others who are also part of the universe. It is a vision that gives security, that makes men feel solid, on a broad foundation. Teilhard de Chardin attributed to this feeling an awakening towards ever wider forms of humanity.¹¹⁴ S. Weil even claimed that union with the entire universe causes a kind of symbiosis.¹¹⁵ Psychologist Otto Rank¹¹⁶ sees mental health in it.¹¹⁷ Eastern spirituality has always supported the positivity of this mental orientation.¹¹⁸

Dag Hammarskjöld in his *Markings* wrote: “Our work for peace must begin within the private world of each of us. To build for man a world without fear, we must be without fear. To build a world of justice, we must be just”.¹¹⁹ He perceived the quest for maturity and maturity of mind as basic elements of this attitude.

“Each of us is more than the worst thing we've ever done. My work with the poor and the incarcerated has persuaded me that the opposite of poverty is not wealth; the opposite of poverty is justice,”¹²⁰— Bryan Stevenson says.

We argue also that attempts to have peace, to achieve justice and the regulation of business faltered because so many human beings ranked liberty for themselves higher than equality with others and peace\justice for all. A common cause of war and injustice is

112 Carlo Molari (1928) is an Italian presbyter and theologian.

http://www.rocce.cittadella.org/rocce/autori/00000112_Molari.html

113 Molari Carlo, *The spiritual journey of the Christian*.

THE FOLLOWING OF CHRIST IN THE NEW PLANETARY HORIZON (Italian) (2020)

114 See in detail: King Ursula, *Teilhard de Chardin's vision of science, religion and planetary humanity: A challenge to the contemporary world*, *Journal for the Study of Religion*, vol.31 no.1 Pretoria (2018),

http://www.scielo.org.za/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1011-76012018000100009&lng=pt&nrm=iso&tlng=pt

115 See in detail: Lowtoo Bharatee, *Love for God's Necessity: the ambiguity of Simone Weil's hupomone* (2009),

<http://arno.uvt.nl/show.cgi?fid=96578>

116 Otto Rank (1884–1939) was an Austrian psychoanalyst, writer, and teacher. Born in Vienna, he was one of Sigmund Freud's closest colleagues for 20 years, a prolific writer on psychoanalytic themes, editor of the two leading analytic journals of the era, managing director of Freud's publishing house, and a creative theorist and therapist. In 1926, Rank left Vienna for Paris and, for the remainder of his life, led a successful career as a lecturer, writer, and therapist in France and the United States.

117 See in detail: Hecht Philip J, *The "Fine Line" of Otto Rank* (1994),

<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/231833667.pdf>

118 See *ex grazia*: King Ursula, *Towards a New Mysticism: Teilhard De Chardin and Eastern Religions* Hardcover (1980)

119 Hammarskjöld Dag, UN Press Release SG/360, December 22, 1953.

120 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/7119981-each-of-us-is-more-than-the-worst-thing-we-ve>

human selfishness. As Plato¹²¹ described at length in *The Republic*¹²², people will often commit acts of injustice when they calculate it is in their interests to do so.¹²³

Plato also adds that "The highest reach of injustice is to be deemed just when you are not". War or human injustice is not always caused by attempt to gain unfair advantage or malice; it may be simply the result of the flawed human decision making. With the hungry judge effect for example, studies have found that judges sitting on review boards are less likely to reach decisions favorable to applicants depending on how long it is since the judges had their last food break.¹²⁴ In the monograph titled "Judicial Discretion"¹²⁵, basing on judges interviews, we've found the correlation between in/just judicial discretion and judge's health/well-being.¹²⁶

Misuse and abuse with regard to a particular case or context may represent a systemic failure to serve the cause of justice (within *Judicial Discretion*¹²⁷).¹²⁸ And we miss Liberty, first of all. So it does begin with that understanding.

We've missed Kairos. "Lifetime is a child at play, moving pieces in a game. Kingship belongs to the child".¹²⁹ Thus cryptically, the great philosopher Heraclitus¹³⁰ spoke of lifetime. The lightness of the game, the sense of uncertainty given by a roll of the dice, associated with the mystery of time and its development. It belongs to every human being.

121 Plato (428/427 or 424/423 – 348/347 BC) was an Athenian philosopher during the Classical period in Ancient Greece, founder of the Platonist school of thought and the Academy, the first institution of higher learning in the Western world.

He is widely considered a pivotal figure in the history of Ancient Greek and Western philosophy, along with his teacher, Socrates, and his most famous student, Aristotle. Plato has also often been cited as one of the founders of Western religion and spirituality. The so-called neoplatonism of philosophers such as Plotinus and Porphyry greatly influenced Christianity through Church Fathers such as Augustine. Alfred North Whitehead once noted: "the safest general characterization of the European philosophical tradition is that it consists of a series of footnotes to Plato."

122 *The Republic* is a Socratic dialogue, authored by Plato around 375 BC, concerning justice (δικαιοσύνη), the order and character of the just city-state, and the just man.

In the dialogue, Socrates talks with various Athenians and foreigners about the meaning of justice and whether the just man is happier than the unjust man. The dialogue's setting seems to be during the Peloponnesian War.

123 See the Concept of Injustice by Eric Heinze in https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2039267#:~:text=Heinze%20summons%20ancient%20and%20early,and%20is%20often%20its%20cause.

124 "We find that the percentage of favorable rulings drops gradually from ≈65% to nearly zero within each decision session and returns abruptly to ≈65% after a break." Shai Danziger; Jonathan Levav; Liora Avnaim-Pesso (11 April 2011). "Extraneous factors in judicial decisions". <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3084045/> ; Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America. 108 (17): 6889–92.

Bibcode:2011PNAS..108.6889D. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2011PNAS..108.6889D/abstract> ; For more on the substantial difference in judges' decisions depending on time since last food break, see chpt 3 of *Thinking, Fast and Slow*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thinking,_Fast_and_Slow

125 <http://lib.lawinstitut.ru/ru/virtualexposition/expo1/01-02-papkova.pdf>

126 For more see: Папкина Ольга, Судейское усмотрение (Judicial Discretion), Moscow, 2005, <https://www.twirpx.com/file/183872/>

127 Ibid

128 Edmond N. Cahn, *The Sense of Injustice: An Anthropocentric View of Law* Hardcover (1950), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1051180>

129 As quoted in *The Art and Thought of Heraclitus* (1979) translated by Charles H. Kahn Original: (εἰ) αἰὼν παῖς ἐστὶ παῖζων, πεττεύων παιδὸς ἢ βασιλῆϊ <https://le-cizioni.it/frasi/1933845-heraclitus-eternity-is-a-child-playing-playing-checkers-the/>

130 Heraclitus of Ephesus ("Glory of Hera" c. 535 – c. 475 BC, fl. 500 BC) was an Ancient Greek, pre-Socratic, Ionian philosopher and a native of the city of Ephesus, which was then part of the Persian Empire.

His paradoxical philosophy and appreciation for wordplay and cryptic utterances has earned him the epithet "The Obscure" since antiquity. He wrote a single work, only fragments of which have survived, increasing the obscurity associated with him. Heraclitus has thus been the subject of numerous interpretations. According to the *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, Heraclitus has been seen as a "material monist or a process philosopher; a scientific cosmologist, a metaphysician and a religious thinker; an empiricist, a rationalist, a mystic; a conventional thinker and a revolutionary; a developer of logic—one who denied the law of non-contradiction; the first genuine philosopher and an anti-intellectual obscurantist.

Great modern physics speak to us on time-space, *inter alia*: Carlo Rovelli in “7 brevi lezioni di fisica”¹³¹, Guido Tonelli in “Tempo. Il sogno di uccidere Chronos”.¹³²

Tonelli tells how time is linked to space, how we have learned to govern even time with experiments in quantum mechanics, but also how the dream of governing time in the macro-phenomena of life is still the same dream of our ancestors.

In addition to indicating time with the term Aion¹³³, the Greeks used two concepts: Kronos (Chronos)¹³⁴ - indicates time in its dimensions of past, present and future, the passing of hours- and Kairos - indicates an opportune time, the good opportunity, the propitious moment¹³⁵.

While Kronos (Chronos)¹³⁶ is quantitative, Kairos has a qualitative nature. Chronos is measured and counted, while kairos is lived and experienced.

As the deity Kairos was semi-unknown, the only evidence of the cult of Kairos refers to the altar in Olympia.¹³⁷ It's said in the epigram of the Palatine Anthology¹³⁸ that Menander called the god Kairos while Kronos (Chronos) was considered the deity of the time for excellence.¹³⁹

And so, in our society, we have adhered only to Kronos and have missed Kairos completely. The anxiety (depression, stress) that is typical for our time is nothing more than a rebellion. It's the most common and most widespread formula of the body to express the difficulty in adapting to rhythms, rites and conformisms imposed from the outside. We've missed the integration of external time with one's own, personal and unique internal time. We've missed it, but we we don't feel it. Because it's the lack that doesn't leave space for the thought about time lost.

We've gathered the anxiety, the depression, the stress.

Where does the general dissatisfaction, anxiety, restlessness that oppress souls and cloud minds come from? .. Man lives by chance, ignores the sense of the eternal, shows that he is ignorant of the joy of works that do not serve their immediate builders ... Today man lives poverty in opulence, and risks leaving behind him dilapidation and misery. Nowhere does the fire of enthusiasm shine, the ideal lends his name to the most abject minds. At the bottom of this bewilderment we find the loss of the sense of the divine, the taste of God has been obscured by synthetic vitamins, and life is increasingly flattening. (Giovanni Maria Vannucci¹⁴⁰).

If we do not know how to live in peace and justice, Vannucci's deduction is correct: the taste of the divine is lacking. Our living is dry, something is missing. There is a missing force in life, that vital energy that circulates in creation and makes things, everything, and therefore us too. There is a lack of support that acts from within as an attraction, and requires our free participation, our going towards even the simplest of actions through our actions. There is in this vision a form of mysticism, the Omega that attracts human doing,

131 <https://www.amazon.it/Sette-brevi-lezioni-fisica-Rovelli/dp/8845929256>

132 <https://www.hoepli.it/libro/tempo-il-sogno-di-uccidere-kronos/9788807492921.html>

133 Aion (Greek: Αἰών) is a Hellenistic deity associated with time, the orb or circle encompassing the universe, and the zodiac. The "time" which Aion represents is perpetual, unbounded, ritual, and cyclic: The future is a returning version of the past, later called aevum (see Vedic Sanskrit Ṛtú). This kind of time contrasts with empirical, linear, progressive, and historical time that Chronos represented, which divides into past, present, and future. Aion is thus a god of the cyclic ages, and the circle of the year and the zodiac.

134 He is usually portrayed as an old wise man with a thick grey beard.

135 <http://tomascipriani.it/kronosekairos/>

136 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chronos>

137 <https://oxfordre.com/classics/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780199381135.001.0001/acrefore-9780199381135-e-3523>

138 The Palatine Anthology (or Anthologia Palatina), sometimes abbreviated AP, is the collection of Greek poems and epigrams discovered in 1606 in the Palatine Library in Heidelberg. It is based on the lost collection of Constantinus Cephalas of the 10th century, which in turn is based on older anthologies. It contains material from the 7th century BC until 600 AD and later on was the main part of the Greek Anthology which also included the Anthology of Planudes and more material.

139 <https://resources.warburg.sas.ac.uk/pdf/ekh112b2445785v2.pdf>

140 Giovanni Vannucci (1913 - 1984) was an Italian presbyter and theologian of the Order of the Servants of Mary

that illuminates our going forward along the time line, even the most terrible. A mysticism possible for all as we can all see our time crossed by the divine and therefore sublimated by it.

Modern Europe is a continent and a culture caught in the act of suicide, updated with new Russian and French materials. These include rapid changes in the dynamics of global politics, world leadership, terror attacks across Europe, war, mass immigration, cultivated self-distrust and delusion have contributed to a continent in the grips of its own demise. In France 2020, the factors have come together to make Europeans unable to argue for themselves and incapable of resisting their alteration as a society. We see *quasi* the same thing in modern Russia. Also we observe disappointing failures of multiculturalism, Angela Merkel's U-turn on migration, the lack of repatriation and the Western fixation on guilt, uncovering the malaise at the very heart of the European culture.¹⁴¹

Sociologists and politicians began to clarify the attitude of Europeans to Islam (and the attitude of Muslims to Europeanism) for several reasons:

1- because the percentage of Muslims - both immigrants and *indigenous* residents converting to Islam- began to increase dramatically and Muslims became very noticeable elements of the European *landscape*;

2- because the parties and movements such as The Party for Freedom (Dutch: Partij voor de Vrijheid, PVV)¹⁴² began to appear in Europe - and it is not alone - who have anti-Islamism and anti-immigrantism in their program;

3- because the parties and movement such as International Eurasian Movement (Международное Евразийское Движение, Meždunarodnae Evrazijskoj Dviženie, MED)¹⁴³ began to appear who have the dialogue of confessions and ethnic groups of Eurasia, the commitment to support Shi'i Islam,¹⁴⁴ the wish that all nations be at liberty to pursue their own self-determined lines of development, free from interference and control by US Empire in their program.¹⁴⁵

4- because Muslims from different countries of the Islamic world are less integrated into the cultural environment of their host European countries than the followers of other religions (Jews, Buddhists, Orthodox Christians, Confucians, etc.)

Alexander Ignatenko¹⁴⁶ connects this with the circumstances of the emergence of Islam on the Arabian Peninsula in the 7th century. It emerged in *competition* with Christianity and Judaism already widespread there, and won in that *competition*. The evidence of that *competition* and victory is recorded in the foundations of Islam – in the Koran and Sunnah. And now a Muslim comes to Europe, and if he is a sincere believer and religiously educated, then he experiences a kind of *culture shock* from the fact that the *overcome* religion - Christianity - is dominant in Europe. Further Alexander Ignatenko gives one

141 See in detail: Murray Douglas, *The Strange Death of Europe: Immigration, Identity, Islam*, 2018.

142 The Party for Freedom (Dutch: Partij voor de Vrijheid, PVV) is a nationalist, right-wing populist political party in the Netherlands, founded in 2006.

143 The International Eurasian Movement (Международное Евразийское Движение, Meždunarodnae Evrazijskoj Dviženie, MED) is a non-governmental organization based in Moscow with branches in various European and Asian countries. Its founder and chief executive is the philosopher and political scientist Aleksandr Dugin.

In the 1990s, Aleksandr Dugin developed the philosophical-geopolitical doctrine known as neo-Eurasianism. Soon Dugin decided to support it with an organization capable of leading her to success. In 2000 he created the Eurasia Pan-Russian Political Movement, which the following year turned into a political party in support of President Vladimir Putin (but without competing in the elections). On November 20, 2003, the Eurasia party became a non governmental organization, under the name of "International Eurasian Movement" (Meždunarodnae Evrazijskoj Dviženie, MED).

144 More details: Upton Charles [Sidi Akram], *Dugin against Islam. Realpolitik alliances should not fool committed Muslims*, in: Upton Charles, *Dugin against Dugin: A Traditionalist Critique of the Fourth Political Theory* (2018), <https://crescent.icit-digital.org/articles/dugin-against-islam>

145 <http://med.org.ru/article/1915>

146 Ph.D in Philosophy, head of the Russian Institute of Religion and Politics and a member of the Presidential Council for Interaction with Religious Associations and the Council for Foreign and Defense Policies, who specializes in Arab and Islamic studies and has written extensively on various aspects of Islam.

example: Muslims believe that Allah took to heaven a man, the prophet of true monotheism, the son of Mary named Isa (Jesus), when the Romans came for him with the traitor Judas. Allah gave Judas the features of Isa. And the Romans crucified Judas on the cross, not Isa. It turns out, according to the logic of Muslims, that Christians worship crucified Judas in churches! What do they feel? Shock? Shock.¹⁴⁷

Muslim World was seen as rising to challenge the Christian West. The war now is in Europe, within the same race, faith, civilisation.

The Court states that Shari'a as a system is not compatible with the fundamental values of the Convention.¹⁴⁸ The Court is right, remaining neutral, because there are¹⁴⁹ differences between the sources of law in Civil, Common and Islamic legal systems. One of the main reasons for this is the different origins of law. In Islamic law, God created the law, in Civil/Common law, people made legislations.¹⁵⁰ In Islamic countries, law is considered absolute and constant, whereas it is much more flexible, changeable and negotiable in Civil/Common laws¹⁵¹ "Islamic law" refers to juristic interpretations (fiqh) of divine law (sharī'ah). In 2000, the Court found that there had been a violation of Article 9 in the Hasan and Chaush v. Bulgaria case. The applicants, a former Chief Mufti of the Bulgarian Muslims and a teacher of Islam, complained about the Bulgarian authorities' decision to change the leadership and statute of the Muslim community. The Court found that there had been interference with the internal organisation of the Muslim community and the applicants' freedom of religion.¹⁵²

This paper argues that if one looks at actual cases rather than legal differences, a very different view of Islamic law emerges. The stress is not on antecedent concepts, but consequences. This is consistent both with the legal style and the social relationships within which the law (or a court) is active.

Islam has been rooted in Europe for decades through a huge wave of labor immigration. Hundreds of thousands of Spanish-speaking migrants from Latin America converted to evangelical Christianity in Spain between 1992 and 2008. France has the largest number of Muslims in the Western world. According to the Pew Research Center, Muslims make up 5.8% of the population of France.¹⁵³ According to the latest Eurobarometer poll (2019), on the other hand, the Muslim population in France is 5% of the total population.¹⁵⁴ Islam is the second-most widely professed religion in France (behind only Christianity). The majority of Muslims in France belong to the Sunni denomination.¹⁵⁵ Also in Russia Islam is the second largest religion (up to 20 million people, 10% of the total population), adherents of which follow various directions and tariqa.¹⁵⁶ The majority of Russian Muslims are Sunnis, about 10% are Shiites. *Muslims to make up 30% of Russia's population by 2034.*

147 <https://rg.ru/2010/11/18/islam-site.html>

148 https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Research_report_application_islamic_law_ENG.PDF

149 Juraev Nosirjon, Differences between the sources of law in Civil, Common and Islamic Legal Systems, <https://www.grin.com/document/233559>

150 Juraev Nosirjon, Differences between the sources of law in Civil, Common and Islamic Legal Systems, <https://www.grin.com/document/233559>

151 Juraev Nosirjon, Differences between the sources of law in Civil, Common and Islamic Legal Systems, <https://www.grin.com/document/233559>

152 <https://minorityrights.org/wp-content/uploads/old-site-downloads/download-382-Hasan-and-Chaush-v-Bulgaria.pdf>

153 5 facts about the Muslim population in Europe, Pew Research Center, <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2017/11/29/5-facts-about-the-muslim-population-in-europe/>

154 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Islam_in_France

155 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Islam_in_France

156 Tariqa is a term adopted in Islam to designate a Sufi order or school that practice a special mystical teaching and spiritual practices for the intimate comprehension of divine truth and achieving spiritual self-improvement.

List of Sufi orders see here: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Sufi_orders

On the Religious Movements THE SUFIS see here:

https://www.academia.edu/9422575/Religious_Movements_THE_SUFIS

On the Sufi Levels of Self and the Enneagram Levels of Development see here:

<https://enneagramegypt.com/f/the-sufi-levels-of-self-and-the-enneagram-levels-of-development>

Number of Muslims in the country has been increasing every day, says Russia's grant mufti.¹⁵⁷ Islam in Russia is a complex, transversal and multidimensional issue and its growing importance in Russia will shape the future of the country in at least five main directions: the overall demographic balance of the country; the strategy of *normalizing* the regions of the North Caucasus; Russia's migration policy; Russia's positioning on the international scene; and the transformation of Russian national identity.¹⁵⁸

Historically, many different nationalities live on the territory of Russia. Despite the fact that they differ from each other in traditions, culture and religion, since ancient times all peoples communicated with each other, traded, exchanged experiences, traditions and culture.

M.Antonov is right, confirming that "Religion, morality, and the law work together in Russia in a rather specific manner—with no prevalence on the part of the law (which is expected from a state based on the rule of law) and with rights being subject to concerns of sovereignty".¹⁵⁹

Here it should be noted that the peoples of Russia did not adopt other people's traditions and culture, but accepted it and treated it with respect, not condemning it, not humiliating it. An example is the traditional Tatar holiday Sabantuy.¹⁶⁰ Recently, this holiday has become an all-Russian one, that is, it is now celebrated not only in the Republic of Tatarstan, but throughout Russia.

Now we're putting attention to the war in Ukraine and to the French Interior Minister Gérald Darmanin who speaks of France fighting a *civil war*. "They want our death. So we will fight them to the death"¹⁶¹, -the French President is reported to have said. "The French Republic is a nice girl but she won't allow herself to be raped".¹⁶² To defend France's secular and unitary Republic against the *separatist* teaching of extremist Islam he suggests that ethnic food aisles in supermarkets should be closed. In other words: Let's punish the innocent as well as the guilty ones...

The invasion of Ukraine has exposed anti-Arab and anti-Muslim bias across European policymaking and news media. In the most recent incident — a textbook case of double standards — a Danish politician suggested that Ukrainian refugees could be exempt from laws that had allowed authorities to seize the assets of Syrian and Iranian refugees.

Rasmus Stoklund, immigration spokesman for Denmark's Social Democratic government, told Danish paper Ekstra Bladet that the so-called jewelry law should not be applied to Ukrainians fleeing the conflict because they are from a "nearby region."

Later, Stoklund said: "The jewelry law is made for if you leave the nearby region where you are safe, and travel through safe countries ... but that is not the case for Ukrainians."¹⁶³

How to organize for different peoples the Sabantuy¹⁶⁴ holiday but not the current Sabantuy war?

157 <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/world/-muslims-to-make-up-30-of-russia-s-population-by-2034-/1409181>

158 Laruelle Marlene, How Islam Will Change Russia. The Jamestown Foundation (September 13, 2016)

159 Antonov Mikhail, Conservative Philosophy and Doctrine of Sovereignty: A Necessary Connection?, Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie No.153, 45-59 (2017)

160 Sabantuy is a Tatar, Idel-Uralian and Bashkir summer festival, that dates back to the Volga Bulgarian epoch.

Sabantuy traces its origins to the pre-Islamic epoch, when it was celebrated before the sowing season. The presence of Sabantuy was noticed by ibn Fadlan as early as in 921. Traditional songs and other customs of the Sabantuy probably had a religious connotation at that time. Later, with the spread of Islam among Tatars and Bashkirs and Christianity among Chuvashs, it became a secular holiday. In each region, villages took turns to celebrate the holiday.

In the beginning of the 20th century Sabantuy gained recognition as the national festival of the Tatars.

Recently, Moscow announced plans to nominate Sabantuy for the inclusion into the Masterpieces of the Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity list. (See: Drayton James. "Sabantuy", home to roam (4 July 2012), <http://hometoroam.blogspot.com/2012/07/sabantuy.html>)

161 <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/10/27/world/europe/French-Muslims-Turkey-crackdown.html>

162 <https://www.politico.eu/article/on-islam-macron-is-more-measured-than-his-critics-claim/>

163 <https://www.arabnews.com/node/2038816/media>

164 Using Sabantuy as *Allgemeinbegriff*, the general notion.

Of course, great F. Tyutchev¹⁶⁵ is right, writing in one of his philosophical monostrophe miniatures¹⁶⁶:

You cannot grasp Russia with your mind
Or judge her by any common measure,
Russia is one of a special kind –
You can only believe in her.¹⁶⁷

Let's do science and not war: we appeal for peace. And there is enormous room for compromise with Russia.¹⁶⁸ Russia's experience in balancing secular and religious values and peaceful coexistence of peoples is important for the international community. "Our model of interreligious cooperation and current Russian statutes do not allow the citizens of Russia, our society to make disrespectful statements about issues of faith and beliefs of people,¹⁶⁹ -A. Shkolnik¹⁷⁰ says.

"Without Russia, the German bloodhounds would have already achieved their goal, or would achieve it very soon. [...] we and our children owe a great debt of gratitude to the Russian people for having experienced such immense losses and suffering. [...] [Russia's] conduct the war has made obvious her great achievements in all industrial and technical fields. [...] and in the limitless sacrifice and exemplary self-denial of every single individual, I see proof of a strong and universal will to defend what they have won. [...] In Russia the equality of all national and cultural groups is not merely nominal but is actually practiced!,¹⁷¹-Einstein said.

Although some scholars argue against comparing Western and Eastern Europe, we suggest that it is possible to evaluate balancing secular and religious values and peaceful coexistence of peoples among all European countries.

It is perhaps that the roots of the war, anxiety (depression, stress) of the modern world can be traced in the Kairòs missing. Therefore, we, trivially focused on the quantity of doing and homologated in the flattening 'having', have missed the personal specialty and therefore the quality of being.

We've studied Florensky's conception of time in *The Meaning of Idealism* (1914), where he first confronts Einstein's theory of special relativity, comparing it to Plato's metaphor of the Cave and Goethe's myth of the Mothers.

Later, in his *Analysis of spatiality and time*, Florensky speaks of a person's biography as a four-dimensional unity, in which the temporal coordinate is examined in sections.

In *On the Imaginaries in Geometry* (1922), Florensky argues that the speed of light is not, as in Relativity, an absolute speed limit in the universe. When bodies approach and then surpass the speed of light, they are transformed into unextended, eternal Platonic forms. Beyond this point, time runs in reverse, effects precede their causes, and efficient causality

165 Fëdor Ivanovič Tyutchev (1803 - 1873) was a writer and eminent Russian poet, diplomat. He lived in Munich and Turin, he knew Heine and Schelling. He did not participate in literary life and did not call himself a man of letters.

166 In addition to this poem, Tyutchev wrote several other philosophical monostrophe miniatures (*When the last hour of nature strikes, Nature is a sphinx, It is not given to us to predict*) See in detail: Valiulis Svetlana, Reference book on literary criticism (2004)

167 Tyutchev's lines have also recently become popular with politicians. Some years ago when welcoming French President Nicolas Sarkozy in the Kremlin, Vladimir Putin cited these lines, albeit revising the last line to say *You should only believe in her*. The verse also appeared in the remarks of former French President Jacques Chirac when he visited to Kremlin to accept a state award from Russia: <https://polit.ru/news/2008/06/13/5000000/>
See in detail: Tsonchev T.S, RUSSIA AND THE WEST:FYODOR TYUTCHEV ON RUSSIAN EXCEPTIONALISM, The Montréal Review (September 2018), <http://www.themontrealreview.com/2009/Russia-and-the-West-Fyodor-Tyutchev-on-Russian-Exceptionalism.ph>

168 <https://www.dire.it/13-03-2022/715093-ucraina-carlo-rovelli-basta-armi-rischiamo-un-altro-novecento/>

169 <https://www.oprf.ru/ru/press/news/2617/newsitem/56247?PHPSESSID=510o20fkf6ifui9i2acffngsd0>

170 Aleksander Shkolnik (1964) is the Russian statesman, director of the Central Museum of the Great Patriotic War since April 28, 2017. According to the decree of the President of the Russian Federation, in 2020 he became a member of the Public Chamber of the Russian Federation, elected Deputy Secretary of the Public Chamber of the Russian Federation. He is the Member of the Public Chamber of Moscow of the III convocation (2019).

171 From the speech to the Jewish Council for Russian War, 453-454 (25 October 1942)

is transformed into final or teleological causality, a concept on which Florensky elaborates in his *Iconostasis*.

Florensky thus transformed the findings of Einsteinian relativity in order to make room for Plato's intelligible Ideas, the Aristotelian distinction between a changing realm of earth and the immutable realm of the heavens, and the notion of teleology or final causation. His notion that man can approximate God's vision of past, present and future all at once, as if from above, is reminiscent of Boethius' ideas.

We've missed happiness and beauty. We've got cowardice, pusillanimity, abuses. We've got ugly-faces and disorder. "Justice can be beautiful. Reconciliation can be beautiful. Repair can be beautiful. It's powerful to actually experience redemption,"¹⁷²- Bryan Stevenson says. And we agree. In our previous papers we've already concluded that Justice is a beauty.¹⁷³ Martin Firrell¹⁷⁴ tells us about „the immense beauty, the vast almost unbearable beauty of justice”.¹⁷⁵ We say on the beauty of Peace.

Here we're talking about Higher Consciousness and fire, an incendiary breath, a creative activity. A judge is in the middle, on the one hand he must listen to the impulses of a world that needs something, and the parties who ask something from the court and on the other he has a discretionary power, the legal possibility to apply creativity.

When Peace\Justice arrives it is like finally freeing the energies. As if it were an irrepressible race, the power and the beauty. Finally Discretion, creativity can explode, it is no longer a question of classical justice\peace, no longer of formal, external, that is a human task, noble yes but that any jurist\politician could understand. To comprehend Peace\Justice there is a creativity, discretion, a Fire, like a running horse. Here there is the burning dream of losing any protection, getting rid of the cloak and no longer having any tight garment. Here there is the fire of creativity and it is no longer enough to share case-law, you have to become Peace and Justice. The fire would have transformed judges into justice and justice into judges, torn apart by the desire to feed on Higher Consciousness. Here the horse is on fire and irrepressible, only freedom! The horse is free
Peace\Justice is still a long way off, peace\justice is not divided, power reigns. Mystical judges know this. It is necessary to fight for this right. It seems human to us. Very human. If you do not feel the scandal of war and injustice within you, you are inhumane. Fighting for peace and justice, fighting again. But doing it on oneself, it also seems unavoidable to us. Because we too are guardians of evil. For a long time we no longer believe in those who stun us with great campaigns of planetary justice and peace if they do not first show us their fragility.

But we cannot forget the fire. Peace\Justice is not enough for us, even if there is no longer a victim in the world, even if there is only good in the world, it is not enough for us. We need someone who shares a fire and a race, a love so radical that it cannot be contained in the categories of right. We want the madness of a running horse, we want a scorching court that doesn't always and only bring us back to the law and case-law. It is not enough for us, it is not enough at all. And we're sure even the Baptist would no longer be enough because when you meet Fire, an etiquette of peace\justice is not enough ..

The Court is not a refuge for sad people, the Court is the home of joy! And those who are

172 <https://www.vox.com/21327742/bryan-stevenson-the-ezra-klein-show-america-slavery-healing-racism-george-floyd-protests>

173 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1 ; Olga Nickole Papkova Kuyan. Social Values in Europe. Protecting Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Religion, Creating What?: Justice, Sophia, Phronesis. Authorea. July 14, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.162626095.53333722/v1

174 Martin Firrell is a British public artist whose works challenge unjust power systems of all kinds, including patriarchal power, the oppression of women and non-heterosexuals, and the heteronormative status quo. He uses language to engage directly with the public, provoking dialogue about more equitable social organisation. The artist's reported aim is 'to make the world more humane'. His work has been summarised as 'art as debate'.

175 <https://quotepark.com/quotes/1797620-martin-firrell-the-immense-beauty-the-vast-almost-unbearable-bea/>

sad find joy in it, they find true joy and true justice in it!

Love and do what you want - sings that poet by Vasco Brondi ... who is Sant'Agostino ... Peace\Justice is based on happiness.¹⁷⁶ Staying peacefully, justicely¹⁷⁷ is ground on happiness. Staying justicely and staying healthy\peacefully are *quasi* the same thing. War and injustice are disorder, some kind of disease. Patch Adams¹⁷⁸ says "Being happy is the best cure of all diseases!"¹⁷⁹ We find this statement beautiful and correct. And following it, we place peace and justice in being well, in happiness, which is not explosion, but a simple day in the life of a judge\lawyer\politician, the things in which a judge / lawyer expresses himself, his authentic and genuine being, the essence of himself. All the things we have no one misses. But often these things are the elements of war, injustice, dissatisfaction and unhappiness. Angry judge\lawyer\politician will be in war and injustice, always.

People all, judges/lawyers/politicians including, want very simple and natural things. We have come to a conclusion that boils down to two lines: Man does not need God, religion or anything else. A person just wants to be protected, calm and happy, to live in abundance.

Law and intelligence have nothing to do with this. But to protect their rights men go to authorities. Alexei Malashenko¹⁸⁰ shares the opinion that Muslims went to France for happiness, for being protected and calm. When there was the first massive wave of emigration in the 70s of the XXth century, the French said that they were ready to assimilate the newcomers. But the Muslims have been feeling offended. They say "Europeans humiliate us, write bad things about our prophet".¹⁸¹

Five words are sufficient to stop the Ukraine madness: "NATO won't expand to Ukraine". Really, so hard to say them?

Et sic, as long as judges, politicians themselves do not unload the warehouse of things they carry on their shoulders, they will not protect the human rights of others, because they will continue to accumulate this load. They do not want to confront a single thing until this warehouse is overflowing and human rights are completely frozen. They become so insensitive that they can no longer contact themselves, with their rights of human being, let alone the others and their human rights. The authorities want really to protect the rights of human being, but they cannot interconnect normally, in a healthy way. Zygmunt Bauman noted: "We live in a globalising world. That means that all of us, consciously or not, depend on each other. Whatever we do or refrain from doing affects the lives of people who live in places we'll never visit".¹⁸²

The declarations of Orthodox countries in favor of Italy in the Lautsi may be understood along the same lines. These countries are particularly attached to the religious dimension of their culture and reluctant to embrace western post-modernity. Several Orthodox Churches (Churches of Ukraine, Serbia, and Bulgaria) even formally intervened through a letter to the Court. Others publicly took a stand. For example, in a letter to the Italian Prime Minister, Patriarch Kirill of Moscow and all Russia declared that "European democracy should not encourage Christianophobia like atheistic regimes did in the past".¹⁸³ He added

176 See more: John Stuart Mill, Happiness, Justice and Freedom: The Moral and Political Philosophy (1992)

177 <https://www.powerthesaurus.org/justicely/definitions>

178 Hunter Doherty "Patch" Adams (1945) is an American physician, comedian, social activist, clown, and author. He founded the Gesundheit! Institute in 1971. Each year he also organizes volunteers from around the world to travel to various countries where they dress as clowns to bring humor to orphans, patients, and other people. Adams is currently based in Urbana, Illinois. In collaboration with the institute, he promotes an alternative health care model.

179 Jason Marsh, Playing Doctor: An interview with Patch Adams, <https://le-citazioni.it/frasi/160987/history/>

180 Alexei Vsevolodovich Malashenko (1951) is Soviet and Russian orientalist, Islamic scholar and political scientist. Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor. One of the leading Russian experts on Islamic problems.

181 <https://www.bbc.com/russian/features-54907557>

182 Quoted in <https://www.brainyquote.com/authors/zygmunt-bauman-quotes>

183 Letter from Patriarch Kirill, Russian Orthodox Church, to the Italian Prime Minister (Nov. 26, 2009) available at <http://www.mospat.ru/en/2009/11/26/news9194>

that "the Christian heritage in Italy and other countries in Europe should not become a matter to be considered by European human rights institutions . . . the pretext of ensuring the secular nature of a state should not be used to assert an anti-religious ideology, which apparently violates peace in the community, discriminating against the religious majority in Europe which is Christian".¹⁸⁴

The interventions of twenty-one Member States to support Italy in *Lautsi v Italy* case demonstrate that the postmodern model of liberal democracy, cut off from its cultural and religious roots, has not entirely conquered Europe. It may even be drawing back, due to the social and cultural constraints imposed by globalization. Z. Bauman is sure: "Globalization is the last failed hope that, somewhere, there still exists a land where one can escape and find happiness. Or the last failed hope that, somewhere, there still exists a land different from yours in terms of being able to oppose the sense of meaninglessness, the loss of criteria and, ultimately, moral blindness and the loss of sensitivity".¹⁸⁵ Sometime around 400 BC, the Greek philosopher Thucydides¹⁸⁶ wrote "the secret to happiness is freedom... and the secret to freedom is courage."¹⁸⁷ This is a simple truth, but one that still holds today.

A century after the pioneering Canadian philosopher, psychiatrist, and nature-explorer Richard Maurice Bucke drew inspiration from Whitman to develop his theory of cosmic consciousness¹⁸⁸, and a century before the emerging science of counterfactuals threw its gauntlet at our fundamental assumptions about the nature of the universe, Schrödinger takes up the parallels between the discoveries of quantum physics and the core ideas of the Hindu philosophy of Vedanta.¹⁸⁹ "Creativity requires the courage to let go of certainties."¹⁹⁰ — Erich Fromm said.

We've missed the internal reality. We've paid attention¹⁹¹ to the external reality. Our interiority seems small in comparison with Law, its Rules, Principles, Practice (case-law).

The contrast between the two worlds could not be greater, because the study of the external Justice is based on Law, legal norms, appropriate justice system among other systems, law enforcement, including policies, and on sharing law interpretations and case-law. While the study of the internal is "subtle", because consciousness is personal and shareable only partially.

The lawyer/judge is placed in the position of perceiving more the cases, the judgements and decisions, the difference between the judicial practice, case-law, what we call justice

184 Ibid

185 Bauman Zygmunt, *Moral Blindness: The Loss of Sensitivity in Liquid Modernity* (2013)

186 Thucydides (c. 460 – c. 400 BC) was an Athenian historian and general. Thucydides has been dubbed the father of "scientific history" by those who accept his claims to have applied strict standards of impartiality and evidence-gathering and analysis of cause and effect, without reference to intervention by the deities, as outlined in his introduction to his work.

He also has been called the father of the school of political realism, which views the political behavior of individuals and the subsequent outcomes of relations between states as ultimately mediated by, and constructed upon, fear and self-interest. His text is still studied at universities and military colleges worldwide. The Melian dialogue is regarded as a seminal work of international relations theory, while his version of Pericles' Funeral Oration is widely studied by political theorists, historians, and students of the classics.

More generally, Thucydides developed an understanding of human nature to explain behavior in such crises as plagues, massacres, and civil war.

187 <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/classics/research/thucydides/ttt/text/>

188 <https://www.amazon.it/Cosmic-Consciousness-Study-Evolution-Human/dp/1535081562>

189 http://michel.bitbol.pagesperso-orange.fr/Schrodinger_India.pdf

190 <https://www.passiton.com/inspirational-quotes/7487-creativity-requires-the-courage-to-let-go-of>

191 Earlier we've already written on the significance of the attention. See, inter alia, Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021).

Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, Calling to Have the Courage to Make Changes. *Mindfulness Matters: Thought, Attention, Awakening*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734445>

and we think it exists as we see it; and less the internal world, judge/lawyer/person's interiority, to which lawyers/judges generally give little importance.

Our experience can make you aware of this situation, since we too have an interior, which we may not care much about and which perhaps we have little awareness of, exactly as it was happened to Faggin who for a good part of his life lived taken by the research and study of what is outside and did not worry about the existence of his own interiority.¹⁹²

Instead, we must consider that we know directly and deeply only the inner world, while the knowledge of the outer world - what we call the real - takes place not only through our senses but also through means built by ourselves, and it is an objective world, the whose knowledge is incontrovertible and shared. We have direct, personal, individual and only partially communicable knowledge of our interior.

We pay attention to many external things we see big and important: the secularism, the separation of church and state, *inter alia*, and we miss the Higher consciousness.

Courts are part of the judicial branch of government. A court settles disputes through a legal process. Resolving a case, the court applies the Rule of Law. Constitution is the supreme law of the land.

According to the article 14 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, the Russian Federation shall be a secular state. No religion may be instituted as state-sponsored or mandatory religion.

Religious associations shall be separated from the state, and shall be equal before the law.¹⁹³

Also France is a secular country in that it claims it is officially neutral in matters of religion, supporting neither religion nor the absence of it, as well as not having a state religion.

The Constitution of 1958 states: "France is an indivisible, secular, democratic and social Republic, guaranteeing that all citizens regardless of their origin, race or religion are treated as equals before the law and respecting all religious beliefs".¹⁹⁴

"The French state does not favour any one religion and guarantees their peaceful co-existence in respect of the laws and principles of the Republic", - the government's website reads.¹⁹⁵

Must a society be secular to be democratic? This is in substance what the applicants claimed in Lautsi v Italy case: "the principle of secularism coincides with the principle of democracy. A non-secular State could not be considered democratic."¹⁹⁶

This opinion is conceivable from a philosophical point of view, provided democracy is considered necessarily liberal by nature, as it is presently in most western States. Indeed, the principles of liberalism ultimately imply a certain moral relativism, and consequently a privatization of religion. According to this view, Western democracies are thus secular, at least in their essence.

Affirming that a democratic State is necessarily secular is unrealistic; moreover, it infringes the sovereignty of the Member States which have never undertaken such an obligation.

What was at stake in the Lautsi v Italy case was the determination of the ideological system, either liberal or Christiandemocratic, directing the interpretation of the Convention.

In the case it clearly appears that, in the context of the European Convention, democracy does not imply secularism.¹⁹⁷

192 See: Federico Faggin, *Silicio. Dall'invenzione del microprocessore alla nuova scienza della consapevolezza*, Mondadori (2019); Federico Faggin, *Silicon: From the Invention of the Microprocessor to the New Science of Consciousness* (2021).

193 <https://www.departments.bucknell.edu/russian/const/ch1.html#:~:text=Article%2014.,be%20equal%20before%20the%20law.>

194 <https://www.diplomatique.gouv.fr/en/coming-to-france/france-facts/secularism-and-religious-freedom-in-france-63815/article/secularism-and-religious-freedom-in-france#:~:text=Secularism%20Today-.Introduction,states%20the%20Constitution%20of%201958.>

195 <https://www.euronews.com/2020/11/05/what-is-secularism-and-why-is-it-causing-such-divisions-in-france>

196 Observations of the applicants for the hearing of June 30, 2010, p. 6.

197 Puppink Grégor, *Opt. cit.*, 897

But namely in the name of French secularism, Macron expressed his determination to *build in the country "enlightened Islam" that can be at peace with the French Republic*, to train imams locally, to limit access to private Islamic schools, and to strictly control the activities of cultural and sports associations, which in turn triggered anti-French protests in many Muslim countries.

His remarks angered Muslims all over the world. The head of Chechnya, Ramzan Kadyrov said that he is not ready to "silently watch how the atheists mock religion".¹⁹⁸ Might judges follow similar initiatives?

Judges shouldn't allow for such measures. State authority wants to control the religions more, but to do so, a state authority must give them more legal rights, without building one religion.

Thus, in Russia, a number of ministries, departments, government agencies have their own religious temples, often there are public councils for covering religious topics in these ministries, departments. An ecclesiastical court, also called court Christian or court spiritual, is in modern Russia. In October 2012, the Department of Theology¹⁹⁹ appeared at the National Research Nuclear University MEPhI (Moscow Engineering Physics Institute)²⁰⁰, aimed at mindful interdisciplinary study and research. The Department offers optional courses, special courses of choice, without confessional restrictions: History and Monuments of Christian thought, Contemporary history of religions in Russia, History of Russian science, Social history of Soviet physics, Scientific thought in a general cultural context: the formation of scientific programs, Current trends in the humanities, History of Christian art, Russian language (Academic writing), Research paradigm in social sciences. The academic subject *Fundamentals of Religious Cultures and Secular Ethics* appeared at Russian schools, and a new position of the military priest (chaplain)²⁰¹ appeared in the staff of the Russian Armed Forces. The chairman of the Spiritual Directorate of Muslims of the Saratov Region²⁰², Muqaddas Bibarsov²⁰³ said that it is necessary that the spiritual pastor, the imam-chaplain, should regularly turn to the Muslim military personnel. The mufti also called on the command of the armed forces to respect the food and ritual culture of Muslims, to understand "the difficult geopolitical and ethno-demographic conditions in which the Russian army exists today and will exist tomorrow".²⁰⁴ Bibarsov declared that the muftis are ready to agitate Muslims to serve in the Russian army. The Mufti noted that "in Islam to serve in order to protect the native land is a sacred duty, it is called" jihad", therefore none of the Muslims has ever refused to serve in the Armed Forces, neither in peacetime, nor during an armed struggle".²⁰⁵ The war in Ukraine is a religious one and the implications it may have on the future of the global Orthodox Church.²⁰⁶

198 <https://www.bbc.com/russian/features-54907557>

199 <http://theology.mephi.ru/>

200 National Research Nuclear University MEPhI (Moscow Engineering Physics Institute) is one of the most recognized technical universities in Russia.

201 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Military_chaplain

202 See in detail: Matsuzato Kimitaka, Muslim Leaders in Russia's Volga-Urals: Self-Perceptions and Relationship with Regional Authorities, *Europe-Asia Studies*, Vol. 59, No. 5. 779-805 (Jul., 2007)

203 <http://lizagubernii.ru/ppage/17412/biografiya.html>

204 <https://ria.ru/20201126/muftiy-1586418839.html>

205 <https://ria.ru/20201126/muftiy-1586418839.html>

206 <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/religionglobalsociety/2022/03/russias-invasion-of-ukraine-the-first-religious-war-in-the-21st-century/>

As for France, Geneva-based researcher Reda Benkirane²⁰⁷, who has studied contemporary Islam and inter-religious dialogue in both France and Switzerland, says Macron's vision goes against a cornerstone of French society: the separation between religion and state.

"The irony is that while Macron is leading the defence of secularism in France, his proposals are actually reinforcing state intervention to shape the religious convictions of its citizens",²⁰⁸ - the Swiss researcher says.

Under the traditional standard, religious reasons could permissibly animate public decision-making so long as there was a distinct predominant secular purpose.²⁰⁹ The Court has recently indicated its willingness to dispose of the secular purpose requirement. In the *Lautsi* ECtHR stated that *secularism* is a conviction and is respectable since it is compatible with the Convention, like many other convictions.²¹⁰ Rather than requiring a primary secular justification, the Court now substitutes a standard that tolerates any conviction for governmental acting. To the extent that there remains a secularism standard, it is no longer meaningful. It is easily satisfied by the assertion of any secular legislative purpose, no matter how transparent, as long as the underlying religious purpose *coincides* with the asserted secular purpose. This is in harmony with the opinion of Ivan Ilyin: "everyone believes: both the free-thinking and the atheist, and the materialist believe; both socialists and communists believe, and persecutors of Christianity".²¹¹

This Court's argumentation corresponds to *Pascal's Wager*²¹², also.

There are two convictions in the secular state: religion and secularism; religion penetrates practically all spheres of public life, including those areas that are separated from religion according to the Constitution: government agencies, schools, the army, education.

In international or European law, there is no precise or generally accepted definition of secularism.

The essence of the State, secular, confessional, or otherwise, is a country's internal affair. In the *Lautsi* in focusing on Italy's nature rather than its conduct, the Second Section placed itself in a position to blame Italy for being what it is, and to require it to act as if it were not so.²¹³

We agree with Trigg that in recent years there has been a clear trend for courts in Europe to prioritize equality and non-discrimination above religion.²¹⁴

Determining it in the *Lautsi*, the Grand Chamber expressed refusal to arbitrate the Italian domestic debate on the meaning of secularism.²¹⁵ It isn't something that the ECtRH is competent to decide.

In the *Lautsi v Italy* case the Court rejected the secularism in favor of the notion of neutrality.²¹⁶

207 Réda Benkirane (1962) is a Swiss sociologist from Morocco, consultant to international organizations in Geneva, specialist in communication. Engaged in various projects of weaving and mixing of knowledge (scientific humanities, digital humanism), his research has focused successively on urbanity, complexity (Benkirane Réda, *La complexité comme manière de remplir et d'habiter l'espace et le temps*", 2ème colloque international francophone sur la Complexité, *La pensée complexe : défis et opportunités pour l'éducation, la recherche et les organisations*, Université Lille 1, 31 mars-1er avril 2010, http://www.archipress.org/reda/?page_id=591), Islamity and radicalism.

208 <https://www.swissinfo.ch/eng/how-switzerland-and-france-approach--islamic-separatism-/46105336>

209 See in detail: Teitel Ruti, *Critique of Religion as Politics in the Public Sphere*, *Cornell Law Review*, Volume 78 (5 July 1993), <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/73975532.pdf>

210 Puppincck Grégor, *The Case of Lautsi v. Italy: A synthesis*, 2012 *BYU L. Rev.* 873, 891 (2012), <https://digitalcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol2012/iss3/7>

211 Read more: Ilyin Ivan, *Collected writings in 10 volumes. Volume 1 (collection) (Russian)* (2017)

212 See Pascal Blaise, *Columbia History of Western Philosophy*, 353.

213 Opt.cit, 914

214 See Trigg Roger, *Free to Believe?: Religious Freedom in a Liberal Society* (2010)

215 Puppincck Grégor, *The Case of Lautsi v. Italy: A synthesis*, 2012 *BYU L. Rev.* 873, 894 (2012), <https://digitalcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol2012/iss3/7>

216 Opt.cit, 892

French domestic law clearly enshrines secularism. Of course, its concept of secularism differs from that of Italy, *inter alia*. But in the Lautsi case the efforts of the Italian government to prove that the crucifix—as a symbol of civilization—supports secularism, instead of opposing it, finally proved useless.²¹⁷ The issue was relevant in the domestic debate, but off topic before the European Court. The government’s presentation still held merit however, describing an original concept of secularism that respects the culture of society instead of aggressively stirring conflict within it.

For Macron and his ministers to talk about civil war, a fight to death and France under siege is not the right way to resolve the nation’s Islamist crisis. *Sabantuy* war seems as the far right prepares to attempt to take over in coming elections, banking on rising hatred and distrust within French society.

“In European countries, the policy is turning towards the interference of regulatory bodies in the life of Muslims”, - Igor Alekseev²¹⁸ says, -“Muslims were not incorporated into the life of society, the state did not know very well what was going on with them. And now they apparently decided to increase control”.²¹⁹ The mainstream organizations have embraced the principles of the Republic, including the separation of church and state, but those on the fringes feel left out and so are easy prey for extremists. Even Macron admitted that the country’s Muslim citizens have been let down by successive governments. He said that France has created its own *separatism* by dumping poorer people in suburban ghettos with poor-quality housing and few jobs. He vowed to right this wrong, but there has been scant follow-up. Mr. Castex, the prime minister, told reporters that France would “build more social housing, better distributed throughout the territory in order to break with the logic of ghettos”.²²⁰ That promises to be a long process with uncertain outcome.

Experts call what is happening in France as another clash between the Islamic world and the West.

Some Europeans have a negative attitude towards Russia, Islam and Muslims. But there is also a positive attitude of some Europeans towards Russia, Islam and Muslims. We won’t give statistics here, it is available on the Internet.²²¹ It is important to understand one thing: judges are witnessing the accumulating and ever-growing mutual hostility of *native* Europeans and a significant part of immigrants arriving from different countries of Ukraine and the Islamic world. Judges are witnessing the state’s failure to integrate many of them into society. Judges are witnessing a man in the street’s (conscience) consciousness and acting.

217 Puppincq Grégor, *Opt.cit*, 898

218 Associate professor of the Department of Contemporary Oriental Studies at the Russian State Humanitarian University; Moscow.

219 <https://www.bbc.com/russian/features-54907557>

220 <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/12/09/world/europe/france-islamist-extremism-bill.html>

221 In 1996, the Runnymede Trust researched public opinions about Islam. The research showed people have different opinions about Islam. The most negative opinions that some people have about Islam are:

That the Islamic World (*Islam*) is seen as a single block that will not change.

That Islam does not have common values with other cultures.

That Islam is inferior to *the West*. It has a barbaric culture, which is also irrational and sexist.

That they think Islam is aggressive and threatening. Some people think it supports terrorism.

That it is seen as an ideology which can be used in politics or war.

That if Muslims criticise *the West*, these criticisms are not tolerated.

That Muslims are discriminated against in society, Islamophobia is used as a justification.

That hostility against Muslims is seen as natural and normal.

<http://www.runnymedetrust.org/uploads/publications/pdfs/islamophobia.pdf>

A study found that Muslim women experienced Islamophobic attacks more often than Muslim men, but almost all are committed by Muslim men. (Siddique Haroon, Muslim Women more likely to suffer Islamophobic attacks than men - study (20 November 2013)– via www.theguardian.com., <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/nov/20/muslim-women-islamaphonic-attacks>)

“One must divide one's time between politics and equations. But our equations are much more important to me, because politics is for the present, while our equations are for eternity”,²²²-Einstein said.

It seems Teilhard de Chardin talks about it, saying: “Such perspectives seem unlikely to the “common sense” of the man in the street and to a certain philosophy of the world for which nothing is possible except what has always existed. Instead they seem completely natural to the mind familiar with the fantastic dimensions of the Universe, because they are purely proportionate to the astral immensities. In the direction of Thought, as in the direction of Time and Space, could the Universe end in something that is not characterized by Dismeasure?”²²³

Here Teilhard says: a *Super-consciousness*, that is a consciousness higher than the one men have, it is possible to develop within the men of the future. Humanity could move towards a broader and more cohesive unity, in which contrasts diminish greatly and there is greater communion; in short, the brotherhood of which Jesus speaks. It is necessary to imagine an evolution that responds to the needs of the quantities that exist in the Universe. Then the idea of *super* union becomes something plausible, not an illogical and senseless thing. If the Universe is immense, the evolutionary process can create something immense. To these considerations he adds the fact that consciousness has always existed in the elements that evolve - he speaks of the *inside of things* - and has always expanded by becoming more and more mature up to our consciousness which is very complex. If this happened in the past, and given that the evolutionary motion does not stop, it can be deduced that the development of consciousness also continues to expand.

It's important to reflect on this idea of the great French paleontologist. Consciousness is not only an experience lived consciously, but it is a process, a constantly evolving flow that men all possess and that diversifies within men and has a social dimension, also. David Bohm²²⁴ hypothesizes two levels of human consciousness²²⁵, one that makes us see a portion of reality and a deeper level where everything is connected in a kind of *continuous wholeness*, a kind of global consciousness that unites us all, especially when there is a strong thought common to many people, but not only is there a type of consciousness in all things that develop following this kind of *program*.²²⁶

Bohm was deeply interested in exploring the nature of consciousness, with particular attention to the role of thought as it relates to attention, motivation, and conflict in the individual and in society.²²⁷

Here we don't speak much on the secularism because it's failed: the secular movement underestimated the endurance of higher consciousness. Secularization is no more a prerequisite for democracy than a reformation of Islam is a condition for rooting democracy in the Middle East. Now scholars are discussing the union of *Islamic gnosis* and *Heidegger's philosophy*²²⁸ as the future of Europe. Claudio Mutti²²⁹, in his *Esploratori del*

222 Quoted in Strauss E, Assistant bei Albert Einstein in Zeit Helle, Zeit Dunkle: In Memoriam Albert Einstein, ed. Carl Seelig, Europa Verlag, Zurich, 38 (1956)

223 <https://medium.com/transumanisti/luomo-come-singularit%C3%A0-evolutiva-e-fenomeno-planetario-3157c4f08482>

224 David Joseph Bohm (1917–1992) was an American scientist who has been described as one of the most significant theoretical physicists of the 20th century and who contributed unorthodox ideas to quantum theory, neuropsychology and the philosophy of mind.

225 On levels of consciousness see here also: <https://www.barrettacademy.com/levels-of-consciousness>

226 More details: Scaruffi Piero. *The Nature of Consciousness* (2006)

227 See David Bohm, *Thought as a System*, Psychology Press (1994)

228 Martin Heidegger (1889-1976) was a German philosopher. He stood in the tradition of phenomenology, primarily Edmund Husserl's one, of the philosophy of life in particular Wilhelm Diltheys and Søren Kierkegaard's interpretation of existence, which he wanted to overcome in a new ontology. The most important goals of Heidegger were the criticism of occidental philosophy and the intellectual foundation for a new understanding of the world.

229 Claudio Mutti (1946), also known as Omar Amin, is an Italian editor, philologist and essayist, of national-revolutionary tendency, convert to Islam. He directs the geopolitical review *Eurasia*. (See in detail: Giovanni Savino, *From Evola to Dugin: The Neo-Eurasianist Connection in Italy*, 97-124, in particular the chapter *Claudio Mutti, The*

Continente²³⁰ reports the fact that during the conference, held in Tehran (2005, the theme Heidegger and the future of philosophy in the East and in the West,²³¹) Shahram Pazouki²³² established a comparison between the medieval Persian philosopher and mystic Suhrawardī²³³ and German philosopher, indicating Islamic gnosis and Heidegger's philosophy as the ideal means for spiritual communication between Asia and Europe.²³⁴ The German philosopher was aware that the profound spiritual decline of Europe, the nefarious result of the bourgeoisie of Christianity, an expression of conventional religiosity without a living faith²³⁵ would deal with a large geographic-spatial dimension still pervaded by profound spirituality, despite the Western nihilism's influence on it. Konstantin Leontiev²³⁶ (the Eurasianism's forerunner) had the same perspective, stated in his fundamental work: today Christianity isn't longer presented as a divine teaching, both terrible and consoling, but as a infantile babble, an allegory, a moral fable, interpreted judiciously in the context of economic and moral utilitarianism.²³⁷ Already at the end of the 19th century Leontiev was aware of the negative influence of the anti-traditional mentality coming from modern Europe on Russian society. He saw a barrier capable of hindering the nihilistic disintegrating phenomenon of the West in a potential alliance between Orthodoxy and Islam. He stated in *Byzantinism and the Slavic world*: "For us, Russians, a fusion with the Asian and non-Christian peoples is more convenient for the simple fact that the modern European spirit hasn't yet penetrated among them, irremediably".²³⁸ This idea was collected and updated by Aleksandr Dugin²³⁹ who, on several occasions, reaffirmed the value of Islam as a bastion of Tradition and the need for a new alliance (*novyj soyuz*)²⁴⁰ between Orthodoxy and Islam; between two traditions that have legitimately inherited the essentials of traditional Eurasian forms.²⁴¹ This perspective has been adopted by various personalities of Islamic culture. The Russian Muslim philosopher, of Azerbaijan origin, Gejdar Dzemaal²⁴² was a proponent of

Prophet, in *Eurasianism and the European Far Right: Reshaping the Europe – Russia Relationship*, ed Marlene Laruelle, Lexington Books (2015)

230 Mutti Claudio, *Esploratori del Continente* (Italian) 2011

231 More details: Derrida Jacques, Gadamer Hans-Georg, Lacoue-Labarthe Philippe, Heidegger, Philosophy, and Politics: The Heidelberg Conference (2016)

232 Dr. Shahram Pazouki is currently Associate Professor of Philosophy and Religious Studies and Head of the Department of Religious and Sufi Studies at the Iranian Academy of Philosophy in Tehran, Iran.

233 Shahāb ad-Dīn, Yahya ibn Habash Suhrawardī, also known as Sohrevardi also known as Sohrevardi, (1154–1191) was a Persian philosopher and founder of the Iranian school of Illuminationism, an important school in Islamic philosophy. The *light* in his *Philosophy of Illumination* is a divine and metaphysical source of knowledge. He is referred to by the honorific title Shaikh al-ʿIshraq *Master of Illumination* and Shaikh al-Maqtul *the Murdered Master*, in reference to his execution for heresy. Mulla Sadra, the Persian sage of the Safavid era described Suhrawardi as the *Reviver of the Traces of the Pahlavi (Iranian) Sages* and Suhrawardi, in his magnum opus *The Philosophy of Illumination*, thought of himself as a reviver or resuscitator of the ancient tradition of Persian wisdom.

234 Mutti C, *Explorers of the Continent. The unity of Eurasia in the mirror of philosophy, orientalism and the history of religions* (Italian), Effepi, Genoa, 100 (2011)

235 Opt.cit, 103.

236 Konstantin Nikolaevich Leontiev (1831-1891) was a Russian doctor, diplomat; thinker of a religiously conservative trend; philosopher, writer, publicist, literary critic, sociologist. At the end of his life he took monastic vows with the name Clement.

237 Leontiev K., *Byzantinism and the Slavic world*, Editions under the banner of Veltro (Italian), Parma, 142 (1987).

238 Opt.cit, 96

239 Aleksandr Gel'evič Dugin (1962) is a Russian political scientist and philosopher. Dugin develops the thought of Martin Heidegger, especially the geophilosophical concept of Dasein, combining it with the thought of the traditionalist school, namely René Guénon and Julius Evola. Dugin played an important role in Russian philosophy. His most important paper is *The fourth political theory* published in 2009

240 Dugin A, *Continent Russia*, Editions under the banner of Veltro (Italian) Parma, 6 (1991)

241 Ibid

242 Geydar Dzhahidovich Dzhemal, sometimes transliterated as Heydar Jamal (1947–2016) was a Russian Islamic public figure, activist, philosopher, poet, political and social activist. He was the founder and chairman of the Islamic Committee of Russia.

this perspective. He saw a powerful factor for opposition to economic imperialism and American cultural hegemony in the strategic alliance between Orthodoxy and Islam.²⁴³ Here, Geviert's idea comes into play - a Heideggerian philosophical model represented through the intersection of two lines similar to the cross of St. Andrew²⁴⁴ - which indicates in its four poles the dimensions of Heaven, Earth, Men and Gods. In the meeting of the quadrature we find the crossroads between heaven and earth, between human and divine. This meeting unfolds the spatial dimension within which it is possible to live in view of the *new beginning*. In fact, the four poles of Geviert have the same Being at the center of the quadrature.²⁴⁵

We've missed the Symphonia. Here we don't intend the Symphonia²⁴⁶ – church-state external relations. We share the Stanley Harakas²⁴⁷'s view that "there are almost no existing presuppositions for its implementation as a system of Church–state relations in our times", and "at most, it presents 'an impossible ideal' in the contemporary world, which may illumine some attitudes for Orthodox Christians regarding their views of the well-ordered state as well as the relationship of the Church toward the state."²⁴⁸ "The apparent problem is that within the framework of "symphonic" cooperation, the Church uses its power to influence the State's legislative and judicial decisions, which is unacceptable in a rule-of-law state."²⁴⁹

We intend the symphonia of consciousnesses. We believe in Higher Total Consciousness as being essential for Justice, a freedom, a free mind. The society in which we live should be organic, where the interests of the individual and society were the same. We are different instruments (or different notes) that can play together in one great orchestra. "We are members of a vast cosmic orchestra, in which each living instrument is essential to the complementary and harmonious playing of the whole,"²⁵⁰— J. Allen Boone²⁵¹ says. Erich Fromm²⁵² was sure: "Spontaneous activity is the one way in which man can overcome the terror of aloneness... for in the spontaneous realization of the self man unites himself anew with the world — with man, nature, and himself."²⁵³ "Not being ourselves is our essential betrayal, not only of our nature but also of the humanity of which we are a part, humanity that needs our uniqueness. "The most beautiful thing we can

243 In this regard, see: Dzermal G., Tawhid; Perspectives of Islam in the former USSR, Editions under the banner of Veltro (Italian), Parma (1993)

244 Heidegger tried not to think of people as the center of the world, but rather in the overall context of a world that he called *Geviert*.

245 See: Heidegger M, On the way to Language (Italian), Mursia, Milan (1973).

246 See on a normative theory or concept in Eastern Orthodox Christian theological and political thought: RUSSIAN ORTHODOX CHURCH, THE BASIS OF THE SOCIAL CONCEPT (2000), <http://orthodoxrights.org/documents/the-basis-of-the-social-concept>

247 Father Stanley Samuel Harakas (1932-2020) was a priest of the Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of America. He is a distinguished teacher of Orthodox theology, and a significant resource in Orthodox ethics. He served as dean of Holy Cross Greek Orthodox School of Theology and Hellenic College where he also taught from 1966 until retirement in 1995. He also was visiting professor at a number of other schools. He has been active in the Ecumenical Movement on local, state and international levels, serving in the Justice, Peace and the Integrity of Creation Commission of the World Council of Churches.

248 Stanley Harakas, Living the Faith: The Praxis of Eastern Orthodox Ethics (1993) 260

249 Mikhail Antonov, Russian Symphonia vs. Rule of Law?, 46 BYU L. Rev. 1183 (2021).

Available at: <https://digitalcommons.law.byu.edu/lawreview/vol46/iss5/7>

250 <https://quotefancy.com/quote/1635482/J-Boone-We-are-members-of-a-vast-cosmic-orchestra-in-which-each-living-instrument-is>

251 J. Allen Boone (17 February 1882 – 17 June 1965) was an American author of several books about nonverbal communication with animals in the 1940s and 1950s.

252 Erich Seligmann Fromm (1900 – 1980) was a German social psychologist, psychoanalyst, sociologist, humanistic philosopher, and democratic socialist. He was a German Jew who fled the Nazi regime and settled in the US. He was one of the founders of The William Alanson White Institute of Psychiatry, Psychoanalysis and Psychology in New York City and was associated with the Frankfurt School of critical theory.

253 <https://www.themarginalian.org/2018/05/07/erich-fromm-escape-from-freedom-spontaneity/>

experience is the mysterious. It is the source of all true art and science. He to whom the emotion is a stranger, who can no longer pause to wonder and stand wrapped in awe, is as good as dead; his eyes are closed. The insight into the mystery of life, coupled though it be with fear, has also given rise to religion. To know what is impenetrable to us really exists, manifesting itself as the highest wisdom and the most radiant beauty, which our dull faculties can comprehend only in their most primitive forms—this knowledge, this feeling is at the center of true religiousness"²⁵⁴, - Albert Einstein confirmed.

The less we are definable, the more we are ourselves. We must be unique, only in this way we enter the process of life that tends to the union of many individual and unique splinters.

We've missed the Daimon. Spirit-energy creates wonders for us as it's described in the Psalm 97.²⁵⁵ Righteousness and justice are its foundation. Fair judges/lawyers have to hope in Higher Consciousness before. St. Paul has described the chronology beautifully: Higher Consciousness is the Whole and includes Christ Consciousness. Also we (judges/lawyers including) are in the Whole. We could be fair/just in Christ Consciousness. The Whole chose us.²⁵⁶ Each person comes into the world because he/she was chosen. Before birth, the soul of each of us chooses an image or design that we will then live on earth, and receives a companion to guide us up here, a daimon²⁵⁷, which is unique and typical for us. However, coming into the world, we forget about this and believe we have come empty. It is the daimon that remembers the content of our image, the elements of the chosen design, therefore he is the bearer of our destiny.²⁵⁸

The idea comes from Plato. Plato in Cratylus²⁵⁹ speculates that the word daimōn (δαίμων "deity") is synonymous to daēmōn (δαίμων "knowing or wise")²⁶⁰, however, it is more probably daiō (δαίω "to divide, to distribute destinies, to allot").²⁶¹ In Plato's Symposium²⁶², the priestess Diotima²⁶³ teaches Socrates that love is not a deity, but rather a "great daemon".²⁶⁴ She goes on to explain that "everything daemonic is between divine and mortal",²⁶⁵ and she describes daemons as "interpreting and transporting human things to the gods and divine things to men; entreaties and sacrifices from below, and ordinances

254 <https://www.forbes.com/quotes/190/>

255 <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Psalm%2097&version=NIV>

256 Following the letter of St. Paul the apostle to the Ephesians 1: 3-6.11-12. <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Ephesians%201&version=NIV>

257 Daimon, gen. daimonos: "lesser god, guiding spirit, tutelary deity", D Harper - Etymology Online, <https://www.etymonline.com/word/demon>, by way of Latin—dæmon: "spirit". "Daimon" itself is thought to be derived from daiomai, with the meaning of to divide or to lacerate. G Agamben; D Heller-Roazen, Potentialities: Collected Essays in Philosophy (1999) 117, Meridian : crossing aesthetics. Stanford University Press, 1999. https://books.google.it/books?id=152xC43N_2kC&q=daimon+etymology&pg=PA117&redir_esc=y#v=snippet&q=daimon%20etymology&f=false

258 See in detail: Erica Francesca Poli, Anatomia della guarigione. I sette principi della nuova medicina integrata (2014)

259 Cratylus is the name of a dialogue by Plato.

260 <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0172%3Atext%3DCrat.%3Asection%3D398b>

261 <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.04.0057%3Aentry%3Ddah%2Fmwn>

262 The Symposium is a philosophical text by Plato dated c. 385–370 BC. It depicts a friendly contest of extemporaneous speeches given by a group of notable men attending a banquet. The men include the philosopher Socrates, the general and political figure Alcibiades, and the comic playwright Aristophanes. The speeches are to be given in praise of Eros, the god of love and desire.

263 Diotima of Mantinea is the name or pseudonym of an ancient Greek woman or fictional figure in Plato's Symposium, indicated as having lived circa 440 B.C. Her ideas and doctrine of Eros as reported by Socrates in the dialogue are the origin of the concept of Platonic love.

264 202d, <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0174%3Atext%3DSym.%3Asection%3D202d>

265 202e, <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0174%3Atext%3DSym.%3Asection%3D202e>

and requitals from above..."²⁶⁶ In Plato's Apology of Socrates²⁶⁷, Socrates claimed to have a daimonion (literally, a "divine something")²⁶⁸ that frequently warned him—in the form of a "voice"—against mistakes but never told him what to do.²⁶⁹ The Platonic Socrates, however, never refers to the daimonion as a daimōn; it was always referred to as an impersonal "something" or "sign".²⁷⁰ By this term he seems to indicate the true nature of the human soul, his newfound self-consciousness.²⁷¹ Paul Shorey²⁷² sees the daimonion not as an inspiration but as "a kind of spiritual tact checking Socrates from any act opposed to his true moral and intellectual interests."²⁷³

Marie-Louise von Franz²⁷⁴ delineated the term daiomai and indicates that its usage is specifically when someone perceived an occurrence which they attributed to the influence of a divine presence, amongst the examples provided by Franz, are from attributing to a daimon the occurrence of a horse becoming or being startled.²⁷⁵

The psychologist Rollo May²⁷⁶ conceives of the daimonic as a primal force of nature which contains both constructive and destructive potentialities, but ultimately seeks to promote totality of the self.²⁷⁷ May introduced the daimonic to psychology²⁷⁸ as a concept designed to rival the terms 'devil' and 'demonic'. He believed the term demonic to be unsatisfactory because of our tendency, rooted in Judeo-Christian mythology, to project power outside of the self and onto devils and demons. The daimonic is also similar to Jung's shadow²⁷⁹, but is viewed as less differentiated. A pitfall of the Jungian doctrine of the shadow is the temptation to project evil onto this relatively autonomous 'splinter personality' and thus

266 Ibid

267 The Apology of Socrates, written by Plato, is a Socratic dialogue of the speech of legal self-defence which Socrates spoke at his trial for impiety and corruption in 399 BC.

268 Plato, Apology 31c–d, 40a; <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0170%3Atext%3DApol.%3Asection%3D31c> ; <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0170%3Atext%3DApol.%3Asection%3D40a>

269 Burnet J, Plato's Euthyphro Apology of Socrates, and Crito (1924) 99–100; Joyal M, To Daimonion and the Socratic Problem, *Apeiron* (2005) vol. 38 no. 2, <https://doi.org/10.1515/APEIRON.2005.38.2.97>

270 Ibid

271 Self-consciousness is a heightened sense of awareness of oneself. It is not to be confused with consciousness in the sense of qualia. Historically, "self-consciousness" was synonymous with "self-awareness", referring to a state of awareness that one exists and that one has consciousness. See: Richard P. Lipka, Thomas M. Brinthaup *Self-perspectives Across the Life Span*, SUNY Press (1992), 228, <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1992-97837-000>

272 Paul Shorey Ph.D., LL.D., Litt.D. (1857–1934) was an American classical scholar.

273 <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Plat.%20Rep.%20496c&lang=original>

274 Marie-Louise von Franz (1915–1998) was a Swiss Jungian psychologist and scholar, known for her psychological interpretations of fairy tales and of alchemical manuscripts.

275 DA Leeming; K Madden; S Marlan (eds.). *Encyclopedia of Psychology and Religion: L-Z* (2010), 197, https://books.google.it/books?id=g0QQtlJSyOEC&q=daiomai+greek+word&pg=PA197&redir_esc=y

276 Rollo Reece May (1909–1994) was an American existential psychologist and author of the influential book *Love and Will* (1969). He is often associated with humanistic psychology and existentialist philosophy, and alongside Viktor Frankl, was a major proponent of existential psychotherapy. The philosopher and theologian Paul Tillich was a close friend who had a significant influence on his work.

As well as *Love and Will*, May's works include *The Meaning of Anxiety* (1950, revised 1977) and, titled in honor of Tillich's *The Courage to Be*, *The Courage to Create* (1975).

277 Zweig, C. & Abrams, J. *Meeting the Shadow*. Tarcher: Los Angeles (1991).

278 Ibid

279 In analytical psychology, the shadow (also known as id, shadow aspect, or shadow archetype) is either an unconscious aspect of the personality that the conscious ego does not identify in itself, or the entirety of the unconscious; that is, everything of which a person is not fully conscious. In short, the shadow is the unknown side. From one perspective, the shadow "is roughly equivalent to the whole of the Freudian unconscious"; and Carl Jung himself asserted that "the result of the Freudian method of elucidation is a minute elaboration of man's shadow side unexampled in any previous age". Contrary to a Freudian definition of shadow, however, the Jungian shadow can include everything outside the light of consciousness and may be positive or negative. Because one tends to reject or remain ignorant of the least desirable aspects of one's personality, the shadow is largely negative. There are, however, positive aspects that may also remain hidden in one's shadow (especially in people with low self-esteem, anxieties, and false beliefs). "Everyone carries a shadow", Jung wrote, "and the less it is embodied in the individual's conscious life, the blacker and denser it is."

unnecessarily fragment the individual and obviate freedom and responsibility. Finally, by comparison to Freud's death instinct (Thanatos)²⁸⁰, the daimonic is seen as less one-sided. While similar to several other psychological terms, noteworthy differences exist. The daimonic is often improperly confused with the term demonic.

Diogo Valadas Ponte and Lothar Schäfer²⁸¹ describe similarities in the ontology of quantum physics and of psychology. In spite of the fact that physics and psychology are usually considered as unrelated, in the last century, both of these disciplines have led at the same time to revolutionary changes in the Western understanding of the cosmic order, discovering a non-empirical realm of the universe that doesn't consist of material things but of forms. These forms are real, even though they are invisible, because they have the potential to appear in the empirical world and act in it. The authors present arguments that force us to believe, that the empirical world is an emanation out of a cosmic realm of potentiality, whose forms can appear as physical structures in the external world and as archetypal concepts in our mind. Accordingly, the evolution of life now appears no longer as a process of the adaptation of species to their environment, but as the adaptation of minds to increasingly complex forms that exist in the cosmic potentiality, in the Whole, in Higher Consciousness.

Federico Faggin shares with us: "I was born into a new life every time i have observed the world from unsuspected points of view, my mind has expanded to new understandings. I was born to new lives when I stopped rationalizing, I listened to my intuition and I opened myself to the mystery."²⁸²

We've missed honesty and responsibility. We know that often judges escape public accountability. And we agree with American colleague Steve Scheckman, that "When you see cases like that, the public starts to wonder about the integrity and honesty of the system".²⁸³ Courts, businesses, banks, insurance companies, people all played a critical role in allowing injustice and supremacy to prevail throughout the 20th century.

We know, among members of the legal profession and judiciary throughout the world, there is a genuine concern with establishing and maintaining high ethical standards. It is not difficult to understand why this should be so. Nor is it difficult to see that professional standards are not completely divorced from ordinary morality. Indeed, legal ethics and professional responsibility are more than a set of rules of good conduct; they are also a commitment to honesty, integrity, and service in the practice of law.

In his book Steven Lubet²⁸⁴ illustrates that law is a vague and boggy realm where truth, and falsehood, is seldom absolute. He explores the complex aspects of honesty in the legal world: Wyatt Earp's shootout with Billy Clanton, Bill Clinton's disastrous decision to lie under oath, Oscar Wilde's self-destructive perjury in a 1896 libel trial, and the dubious resolution of Justice Scalia's duck hunting trip with Dick Cheney are only a few of the cases.

In order to ensure that the standards established are the right ones, it is necessary first of all to examine important philosophical and policy issues, such as the need to reconsider the boundaries between, on the one hand, Judge Duties & Responsibilities, a lawyer's

280 According to Sigmund Freud, humans have a life instinct—which he named "Eros"—and a death drive, which is commonly called (though not by Freud himself) "Thanatos". This postulated death drive allegedly compels humans to engage in risky and self-destructive acts that could lead to their own death. Behaviors such as thrill seeking and aggression are viewed as actions which stem from this Thanatos instinct.

281 Diogo Valadas Ponte, Lothar Schäfer, Carl Gustav Jung, Quantum Physics and the Spiritual Mind: A Mystical Vision of the Twenty-First Century, Behav Sci (Basel). 2013 Dec; 3(4): 601–618, doi: 10.3390/bs3040601

282 Federico Faggin, Silicio. Dall'invenzione del microprocessore alla nuova scienza della consapevolezza Condividi, Mondadori (2019); Federico Faggin, Silicon: From the Invention of the Microprocessor to the New Science of Consciousness Copertina flessibile (2021).

283 <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-usa-judges-misconduct-specialreport-idUSKBN2411WG>

284 Steven Lubet, The Importance of Being Honest. How Lying, Secrecy, and Hypocrisy Collide with Truth in Law (2008)

obligation to a client and, on the other, the public interest. It is also to be appreciated that conflicts of interest are pervasive and that all too often they are so common that they are not recognised as such. Yet rarely is public policy clearly cut.

Oscar Wilde is sure that true honesty is expressed through being genuine to one's self.²⁸⁵ With our paper we force judges/lawyers/everyone of us to rethink how we really feel about honesty and truth.

In the previous papers²⁸⁶ we've examined what lawyers/judges/politicians may learn from the Mindfulness.

We suppose it's local. It's intimate. It's familial, it's communal. It's statewide. It's nationwide. It's worldwide. We think every person, every entity, every institution has to commit to being honest.

We think it's really important that people understand that if you're genuinely engaged and recovering from human rights abuses, you have to commit to truth-telling first. You can't jump to reconciliation. You can't jump to reparation or restoration until you tell the truth. Until you know the nature of the injuries, you can't actually speak to the kind of remedies that are going to be necessary.

Even Leibniz²⁸⁷ claimed that justice is the "charity of the wise or general benevolence" - "*caritas sapientis seu benevolentia universalis*".²⁸⁸ The definition unites the Pauline "charity"²⁸⁹, the Platonic "wisdom"²⁹⁰ and the Augustinian *bona voluntas*.²⁹¹ But if justice is "wise charity", then it cannot merely be about Hobbesian legal justice²⁹² or even the mere prohibition of harming the *neminem laedere* from Roman law. Rather, it must contain a sublimated Platonic "intensification" of the prohibition against harming others²⁹³ to the commandment of charity and enlightened love. This intensification is best described in "Méditation sur la notion commune de la justice" (c. 1703)²⁹⁴, although it is anticipated in the "Codex Iuris Gentium" (1693).²⁹⁵

285 Oscar Wilde, The Importance of Being Earnest, <https://www.bartleby.com/essay/The-Dichotomy-of-Honesty-in-Oscar-Wildes-P3C3SXYZVJ>

286 Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). To Take Law Seriously. Via quantum physics, mechanics. We Vote for Mindful Lawyers/Judges, becoming Political Actors. For Development, Unity of Diversity, Inclusion, Sustainability. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5731565> ; Papkova Olga, Discretionary Justice. Mindfulness. Quantum Theory, Kazan University Law Review, 2021 (w), DOI: 10.30729/2541-8823-2021-6-1-24-66; Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Mindfulness, Quantum Physics and "well-being is a two-way street". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5732075> ; Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, Calling to Have the Courage to Make Changes. Mindfulness Matters: Thought, Attention, Awakening. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734445> .

287 Gottfried Wilhelm (von) Leibniz (1646–1716) was a German polymath active as a mathematician, philosopher, scientist, and diplomat. He is a prominent figure in both the history of philosophy and the history of mathematics. He wrote works on philosophy, theology, ethics, politics, law, history, and philology. Leibniz also made major contributions to physics and technology, and anticipated notions that surfaced much later in probability theory, biology, medicine, geology, psychology, linguistics, and computer science. He wrote in several languages, primarily in Latin, French and German, but also in English, Italian and Dutch.

288 Patrick Riley, Leibniz' Universal Jurisprudence: Justice As the Charity of the Wise (1996)

289 From the first letter to the Corinthians, chapter 13, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=1%20Corinthians%2013&version=NIV>

290 The rule of the wise, Elizabeth S. Belfiore, Socrates' Daimonic Art: Love for Wisdom in Four Platonic Dialogues (2012)

291 From "De Libero Arbitrio",

https://www.bc.edu/content/dam/files/schools/cas_sites/philosophy/pdf/Meaning_of_Voluntas_in_Augustine_Byers_Augstudies_2006_37_2_171_190.pdf

292 <https://www.britannica.com/topic/philosophy-of-law/Thomas-Hobbes>

293 http://www2.units.it/etica/2019_3/KONRADOVA.pdf

294 https://www.pdcnet.org/leibniz/content/leibniz_2005_0015_0000_0185_0216

295 <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/abs/leibniz-political-writings/codex-iuris-gentium-praefatio-1693/C9CB2B58CE1BB5F0A46688ED0F0CBCE4>

Since 1990 Hans Küng²⁹⁶ has launched a fruitful academic and public discourse, including the presentation of the Manifesto for a Global Economic Ethic²⁹⁷ by world leaders at a joint event with the UN Global Compact at the UN headquarters in New York in 2009, calling for business to serve human dignity. Then, Claus Dierksmeier,²⁹⁸ Küng's academic successor and a philosopher, has contributed to the Humanistic Management Project,²⁹⁹ spanning from his conception of qualitative freedom³⁰⁰ as the foundation of unity in diversity to his effort to reframe economic theory and ethics, the inclusive and innovative practices of Humanistic Management,³⁰¹ and to the capability approach.³⁰²

These two different approaches converge in their care for human dignity, the idea of globally responsible freedom, and the capacity for dialogue as a learning process for creative change leadership.

There comes a change that lasts over time. Following Guido Tonelli³⁰³, we could say: "every time I was in trouble, it helped me to ask myself what responsibility I have. Not who else was to blame. If every judge/lawyer/politician/everyone of us was to seek fewer excuses, it would help a lot"³⁰⁴

A just judge/lawyer is the one who is not only filled but transformed by Higher Consciousness.

The attitude of a fair judge is the opposite of that of unconscious judges. In front of Whole, who goes to meet them as a daimon, they hide just as Higher Consciousness tries to help them understand what to do; none of them takes their responsibilities. On the other hand, a conscious judge lets himself to be touched by daimon, trusts him and takes his own responsibility. So a fair judge / lawyer is not only a professional with special education and training, but he/she is the one that the Whole has shaped and continues to shape with his spirit. However, cosmic action towards him/her does not eliminate his/her freedom: he/she is free to choose. And he/she chooses FIAT.

We've missed the small internal thing. And we suppose that we've missed all. Because there aren't small things in the Universe. There is the unique field which penetrates everything, everybody and all. The scientists confirm that there are no particles, there are only fields. They say: there are overwhelming grounds to conclude that all the fundamental constituents of quantum physics are fields rather than particles.³⁰⁵ Quantum fields are the matter. The simplest "practical" quantum field theory is quantum electromagnetism. In it, two fields exist: the electromagnetic field and the "electron field". These two fields continuously interact with each other, energy and momentum are transferred, and excitations are created or destroyed.³⁰⁶ Faggin talks about the quantum field theory (QFT)

296 Hans Küng (1928 – 2021) was a Swiss Catholic priest, theologian, and author. From 1995 he was president of the Foundation for a Global Ethic (Stiftung Weltethos)

297 In the declaration Manifesto for a Global Economic Ethic fundamental principles and values of a global economy are set forth, according to the Declaration toward a Global Ethic issued by the Parliament of World Religions (Chicago 1993). In 2009 the Manifesto for a Global Economic Ethic was presented at a joint event with the UN Global Compact at the UN headquarters in New York. First signatories include renowned international leaders such as Mary Robinson, former president of Ireland, and Archbishop emeritus Desmond Tutu, Nobel Peace Prize Laureate.

<https://www.bbvaopenmind.com/en/articles/the-global-economic-crisis-requires-a-global-ethic/>

298 Claus Dierksmeier (1971) is a German philosopher. He holds a Chair for Globalization Ethics at the University of Tübingen and works as a strategic consultant in politics and business.

299 http://www.humanisticmanagement.org/cgi-bin/adframe/about_us/team/prof_dr_claus_dierksmeier/index.html

300 Claus Dierksmeier, Qualitative Freedom - Autonomy in Cosmopolitan Responsibility (2019),

<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-04723-8>

301 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305713769_What_is_'Humanistic'_About_Humanistic_Management

302 https://www.academia.edu/35407797/Qualitative_Freedom_and_Cosmopolitan_Responsibility

303 <https://twitter.com/ogiannino/status/1148222843668377600?lang=eu>

304 Following the interview: https://lacronacadiravenna.it/articolo/6365/Dante2021.-Il-Poeta_-moderno-e-indispensabile.-INTERVISTA-a-Guido-Tonelli

305 <https://aapt.scitation.org/doi/10.1119/1.4789885>

that is the basis of reality and explains us how quantum fields behave.³⁰⁷ QFT allows us to consider consciousness a quantum field, precisely because of their indeterministic characteristic, which recalls free will. This theory allows to comprehend many inconsistencies that appeared in quantum, when it had not yet evolved with QFT and to create the link with Einstein's general relativity.

There isn't difference between small and big. That's why our little (our micro-) things, our consciousnesses are important, not because of what they are in themselves, but because they are part of something greater, that's why our little things make a big difference, have great power.³⁰⁸ We are embedded in the tissue of the universe. We're like a mustard seed Gesu speaks about: when sown on the ground, it is the smallest of all the seeds that are on the soil; but, when sown, it grows and becomes larger than all the plants in the garden. We're part of the quantum field- of the reality- when we participate in it consciously. The Gospel of Matthew tells us the same thing: The Kingdom of Heaven is like a grain of mustard seed, which a man took, and sowed in his field.³⁰⁹ The small contains big (the whole), the whole contains the small. The small is invisible in the whole. Also relativistic and quantum principles imply that a photon³¹⁰ cannot "be found" at a specific location even in principle.³¹¹ F. Faggin considers particles not as objects, but as "states of fields".³¹² In this paper we attract your attention to the small/great internal. The internal precedes the external. In the previous papers³¹³ we've already delivered the idea that in the procedural field the establishment of judicial discretion by the rule of law is not the judge\lawmaker's whim (desire, caprice) but the result (the fruit) of the development of state\community, law and spirituality.³¹⁴

We've missed Dharma (Dhamma). We've found crutches. We've missed a life of pure Dharma—a life full of peace, harmony and goodwill for others.

The Sanskrit word Dharma (which is spelled Dhamma in the Pāli language) originally meant "the law of nature" or "the truth". The law of nature, in other words, was Dharma. In ancient India Dharma meant that which is imbibed, lived by – dhāretīti dhammam. That which arises on the surface of mind at a given moment was considered the dharma of the mind. What does the mind imbibe but its own nature, its own characteristics, that is its 'dharma'.

The science or technique of looking within was called Vipassana in ancient India. Though one needs to be aware of external reality, to observe within was rightly considered vital for one's mental development; to watch the reactions that arise within due to certain events is one of the most important aspects of consciousness. The day we can truly see this truth, is when we start to understand pure Dharma without any crutches.

Fundamental cosmic law that gathers the various phenomena, makes them live if they conform to its logic or lets them run out if they are not. It governs the world and also we

306 <https://www.forbes.com/sites/quora/2017/12/20/what-is-a-quantum-field-and-how-does-it-interact-with-matter/?sh=75b8178a28c4>

307 <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-nature-of-consciousness/>

308 https://www.openbible.info/topics/little_things_that_make_a_big_difference

309 The Parable of the Mustard Seed is one of the shorter parables of Jesus. It appears in Matthew (13:31–32), Mark (4:30–32), and Luke (13:18–19). In the Gospels of Matthew and Luke, it is immediately followed by the Parable of the Leaven, which shares this parable's theme of the Kingdom of Heaven growing from small beginnings. It also appears in the non-canonical Gospel of Thomas (verse 20).

310 A photon is the smallest possible particle of light, a quantum - of light. A quantum, on the other hand, is the smallest possible particle of any substance at the subatomic level and includes, for example, electrons and neutrinos.

https://it.differbetween.com/article/difference_between_photon_and_quantum

311 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235570468_Why_photons_cannot_be_sharply_localized

312 <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-nature-of-consciousness/>

313 Паркова О.А. Судейское усмотрение (Usmotrenie Suda, Judicial Discretion), Moscva, (2005) 64-199; Olga Parkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

314 Ibid

who are a piece of the world, therefore we have the same logic that tends to order. The day we recognize the universal aspect of Dharma, that day humankind will make a quantum leap in human evolution. If one forgets this universal truth and persists in putting undue attention on the external, then the work of self-evolution slows down, or indeed one moves further away from Dharma.

Dharma is, as said earlier, universal, and has but one yardstick to check whether one is growing on the path; that is to see whether defilements are decreasing. This is the simple and only yardstick to measure Dharma by. Then whichever caste, sect or class one may belong to becomes immaterial once one understands the true and universal nature of Dharma.

The following three are the major constituents of Dharma:

1. Morality (*sila*)

As it is said –

“Manasa ce padutthena, bhasati va karoti va; Tato nam dukkhamanveti, cakkam'va vahato padam.”

-- If with an impure mind one performs any action of speech or body, then suffering follows that person as the cartwheel follows the foot of the draught animal. Similarly – When the mind is pure the actions of body and speech also become naturally pure and their results lead to happiness.

“Manasa ce pasannena, bhasati va karoti va; Tato nam sukhamanveti, chaya'va anapayini.”

-- If with a pure mind one performs any action of speech or body, then happiness follows that person as a shadow that never departs.

When these ambassadors of the Buddha taught people the way to become righteous by attaining control over their minds, then their actions of speech and body naturally became virtuous.

2. Concentration of mind (*Samadhi*) –

It is necessary to attain control over mind for purifying one's actions of body and speech. 'Keep on observing the flow of the normal breath coming in and going out naturally. As soon as the mind wanders away, bring it back to the awareness of the breath. No word should be repeated with the breath; no imaginary belief is to be combined with it. As the breath is coming in and going out naturally, just keep observing it as it is.'³¹⁵

3. Wisdom (*Pañña*) –

As one gets strengthened in the right concentration (*samma samadhi*) on the basis of normal, natural breath, one starts experiencing some sensation near the entrance of the nostrils. Then it starts spreading in the whole body. The truth which one thus realizes is due to one's own efforts. Therefore, it is not indirect knowledge. It is a knowledge gained through one's direct experience. Thus, it is called *Prajña* (wisdom – direct experiential knowledge).

As one works more and more to develop concentration, one comes to realize the three kinds of wisdom.

First is the 'heard wisdom' (*srutmayi Pañña*), which is the knowledge acquired by hearing from someone and accepting it with reverence.

Second is intellectual wisdom (*Cintanamayi Pañña*) which is gained by reflecting over what one has heard from others. When he finds it logical he accepts it. This is called intellectual knowledge gained at the intellectual level by reflection. But both of these are not wisdom in the right sense.

Third is 'experiential wisdom' (*Bhavanamayī Pañña*). This is right wisdom, which is the knowledge gained through one's own experience. Accepting something as true after hearing from others is not real knowledge. The right wisdom is that knowledge which arises

315 Quoted in: <https://www.vridhamma.org/What-is-Dhamma>

through one's own direct experience. It is not indirect knowledge, but it is one's own direct knowledge. Therefore, this is wisdom in the right sense.³¹⁶

Yes, we've missed many things, but Peace\Justice has come near. Believe the good news!

To get peace\justice it's necessary to listen to Higher Consciousness, to Daimon.

To get peace\justice it is necessary to contemplate Higher Consciousness (Justice-Spirit).

To get peace\justice you need to taste Higher Consciousness.

To get peace\justice you need the Nothingness.

To get peace\justice you need to be confident, faithful, courageous, creative.

To get peace\justice it's necessary to be present at the beginning and at the end.

It is not enough to speak about Peace\Justice, but it is necessary to verify the words with actions worthy of peace\justice.

Under "at the beginning" we mean to start from the small thing, becoming a womb for Higher Consciousness's seed that wants and wanted to say and to give herself to the most intimate depths of our history.

Only by becoming the part of us the Consciousness (the Whole) could be listen to, understood and accepted.

Only by humanizing the Whole could indicate the way for judges/lawyers to use humanity as medicine, so that each judge/lawyer could learn to become fair and get Justice finally.

Under "at the end" we mean the moment when justice is mostrated by a judge/lawyer.

We know that among judges no one is greater than a supreme court judge.³¹⁷ But to make justice, to have peace it isn't enough to get extensive education and experience to develop the necessary skills, knowledge and abilities involved with the job. There is something more important than all this: it is the Consciousness field. Yet a first instance judge who touches the Higher Consciousness Field is greater than a supreme court judge. Until now the Higher Consciousness Field has suffering injustice and war. There are judges/lawyers/politicians who have been touching the Higher Consciousness Field, if you are willing to accept it, they are someone in the Know, who are to come. "Let anyone with ears listen!"³¹⁸

We're conscious. We have to see and to listen to, actualy.

316 See more: <https://www.vridhamma.org/Discourses-by-Mr-S-N-Goenka#Dharma>

317 See: Lech Garlicki, Constitutional courts versus supreme courts, International Journal of Constitutional Law, Volume 5, Issue 1, (January 2007) 44–68, <https://doi.org/10.1093/icon/mol044>

318 The same words Jesus said regarding John the Baptist: "Truly I tell you, among those born of women no one has arisen greater than John the Baptist; yet the least in the kingdom of heaven is greater than he. From the days of John the Baptist until now the kingdom of heaven has suffered violence, and the violent take it by force. For all the prophets and the law prophesied until John came; and if you are willing to accept it, he is Elijah who is to come. Let anyone with ears listen!" Matthew 11.11-15, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Matthew%2011:11-15&version=NIV>